

**PILOTs for robotic INSpection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

**Deliverable D10.2
Exploitation and Dissemination Plan**

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Contents

1.	Introduction	10
1.1	Purpose of the document.....	10
1.2	Scope of the document.....	10
1.3	Structure of the document.....	10
2.	Market size analysis	11
3.	Identification of initial Key Exploitable Results (KER)	15
4.	Initial analysis of key exploitable results	20
4.1	KER 1: Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots	20
4.2	KER 2: GNSS-free aerial robot navigation in large areas	20
4.3	KER 3: Hybrid robot for pipes inspection in refineries.....	21
4.4	KER 4: Generic Robot Control Station	21
4.5	KER 5: Texture-based defect detection and classification	22
4.6	KER 6: Quickly building 3D asset models	23
4.7	KER 7: Inspection data overlay on 3D assets.....	23
4.8	KER 8: Asset annotation of key inspection data	24
4.9	KER 9: AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks.....	24
4.10	KER 10: Data Management System	25
4.11	KER 11: Mission Planning Interface	26
4.12	KER 12: Mission Execution by Waypoint Navigation.....	26
4.13	KER 13: Installation of surveying targets by aerial robots.....	27
4.14	KER 14: Tunnel close visual inspection by aerial robots.....	28
4.15	KER 15: Stable contact and crawling by aerial robots	28
4.16	KER 16: PILOTING I&M platform	29
4.17	KER 17: I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization component.....	29
4.18	KER 18: Overall tunnel inspection robot.....	30
4.19	KER 19: Refinery inspection&maintenance robot	31
4.20	KER 20: Mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception.....	31
4.21	KER 21: Localization and Mapping System in Refineries.....	32

5.	Exploitation tools	32
5.1	Early identification of exploitation opportunities	32
5.2	Organization of PILOTING workshops	32
5.3	Value propositions	34
5.4	Pilot demonstrations	35
5.5	Business Model Canvas	36
5.6	Participation in I&M events.....	37
5.7	SoEL impact assessment.....	37
5.8	Participation in standardization groups.....	37
5.9	IP management	38
6.	Exploitation Plan.....	39
6.1	Individual exploitation plans	40
6.2	Exploitation plan per scenario	41
6.2.1	Refinery scenario.....	42
6.2.2	Viaduct scenario	46
6.2.3	Tunnel scenario.....	50
6.3	Initial identification of joint exploitation plans	54
6.4	Industrialization roadmap	57
6.5	Overall exploitation and industrialization timeline	58
7.	Monitoring of the exploitation activities.....	60
8.	Introduction to Dissemination plan.....	60
9.	Dissemination objectives.....	61
10.	Target Audience	62
11.	Dissemination objectives and channels.....	63
12.	Communication and dissemination tools	64
12.1	Communication Tools.....	64
12.1.1	Visual identity	64
12.1.2	Project website.....	64
12.1.3	Social media	65
12.1.4	Radio/TV interviews	67
12.1.5	Periodic press-releases.....	67

12.1.6	Electronic newsletters.....	68
12.2	Dissemination tools.....	68
12.2.1	PILOTING User Group.....	69
12.2.2	Publications	69
12.2.3	Organization of workshops.....	70
12.2.4	PILOTING presentation at relevant events	70
12.2.5	Clustering with other projects and initiatives	71
13.	Monitoring of the dissemination activities.....	72
13.1	Dissemination Procedure	73
13.1.1	Step by step procedure.....	73
	For upcoming dissemination activities.....	73
	For performed dissemination activities	74
13.2	Acknowledgement	74
14.	Conclusions	75
	Annex I: Flyer layout.....	76
	Annex II: Roll-up layout	78
	Annex III: Poster layout	79

List of Figures

Figure 1. The first PILOTING workshop on June 25 th held as a webinar.....	34
Figure 2. Value Propositions Canvas Template.	34
Figure 3. Elements of Business Model Canvas.	36
Figure 4. Overall Gantt for the exploitation and industrialization plans (tasks and activities), and also the activities related to the long-term sustainability of the PILOTING I&M platform	59
Figure 5. Dissemination plan steps.....	61
Figure 6. PILOTING Target Audience.....	62
Figure 7. PILOTING logo.	64
Figure 8. PILOTING LinkedIn profile.	66
Figure 9. PILOTING’s Twitter account	67
Figure 10. EU emblem.	74

List of Tables

Table 1. Acronyms list	9
Table 3. Preliminary market estimation for the three considered scenarios with respect to PILOTING end-users.	14
Table 4. Preliminary market estimation for the three considered scenarios with respect to the EU.....	14
Table 5. PILOTING Exploitable RESULTS.....	19
Table 6. KER 1: Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots.....	20
Table 7. KER 2: GNSS-free aerial robot in large areas.....	21
Table 8. KER 3: Hybrid robot for pipes inspection in refineries.	21
Table 9. KER 4: Generic Robot Control Station.	22
Table 10. KER 5: Texture-based defect detection and classification.....	22
Table 11. KER 6: Quickly building 3D asset models.	23
Table 12. KER 7: Inspection data overlay on 3D assets.	24
Table 13. KER 8: Asset annotation of key inspection data.	24
Table 14. KER 9: AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks.	25
Table 15. KER 10: AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks.	26
Table 16. KER 11: Mission Planning Interface.....	26
Table 17. KER 12: Mission Execution by Waypoint Navigation.	27
Table 18. KER 13: Installation of surveying targets by aerial robots.	27
Table 19. KER 14: Tunnel close visual inspection by aerial robots.	28
Table 20. KER 15: Stable contact and crawling by aerial robots.....	29
Table 21. KER 16: PILOTING I&M platform.....	29
Table 22. KER 17: &M Data Distribution and Harmonization component.....	30
Table 23. KER 18: Overall tunnel inspection robot.....	30
Table 24. KER 19: Refinery inspection&maintenance robot.....	31
Table 25. KER 20: Mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception.	32
Table 26. KER 21: Localization and Mapping System in Refineries.	32
Table 27. Main roles and activities in the execution of the exploitation plan.....	41
Table 28. KER to be exploited in the refinery scenario.	46

Table 29. KER to be exploited in the viaduct scenario.	50
Table 30. KER to be exploited in the tunnel scenario.	53
Table 31. Exploitation KPIs	60
Table 32. Dissemination objectives and channels	63
Table 33. Press release coordinator per country	68
Table 34. List with relevant journals to PILOTING.	70
Table 35. List with relevant conferences and events to PILOTING.	71
Table 36. Dissemination and Communication KPIs	73

Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
ERF	European Robotic Forum
EU	European Union
GSA	European GNSS Agency
IDEM	Innovation, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
SC	Steering Committee
PC	Project Coordinator
WP	Work package

Table 1. Acronyms list

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The deliverable D10.2-Exploitation and Dissemination plan aims to organize the dissemination and exploitation activities to be performed in order to promote, communicate and disseminate PILOTING activities towards the Oil&Gas and the Civil/Transport industry as well as the inspection and maintenance community, robotics society, relevant PILOTING stakeholders, etc., and ensure the sustainability of the PILOTING outcomes after the end of the project.

1.2 Scope of the document

This plan outlines the various dissemination, communication and exploitation tools and activities to be undertaken during the lifetime of the project.

The Exploitation Plan defines the exploitation activities scheduled within the PILOTING project and beyond, to ensure the successful sustainability of the project's results after its termination. The Plan will identify, integrate and synchronise individual and joint exploitation plans of the partners in order to accelerate the market uptake of PILOTING results, including measures for ensuring appropriate commercial exploitation and replication.

The Dissemination plan focuses on the provision of appropriately targeted information about the project existence and achievements to all identified audiences and to ensure liaison with stakeholders. It consists to defining the goals to be achieved, the target groups, the communication and dissemination tools, the procedure for dissemination and the evaluation as well as monitoring the dissemination activities.

The Exploitation and Dissemination Plan is a living document updated during the lifespan of the project to include new actions/strategies resulting from the evaluation of the implemented actions, or to take advantage of new actions/strategies resulting from the evaluation of implemented actions, or to take advantage of newer opportunities that arise.

1.3 Structure of the document

The Exploitation and Dissemination plan and result has the following sections:

- Section 1 describes the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable.
- Section 2 aims to present the market size of PILOTING platform.
- Section 3 presents an overview of the initial key exploitable results (KER) developed within PILOTING project.
- Section 4 offers an initial analysis of the KER presented in the previous section.
- Section 5 describes the exploitation tools which will be used within PILOTING project.
- Section 6 formulates the Exploitation Plan, describing the steps agreed by PILOTING consortium to take PILOTING outcomes to the market.

- Section 7 sets the KPIs for the evaluation and monitoring of exploitation activities.
- Section 8 offers an overview of the dissemination plan of PILOTING project.
- Section 9 identifies the PILOTING dissemination objectives.
- Section 10 identifies the key target audience identify after the initial stakeholders' analysis.
- Section 11 establishes the mechanisms to reach the target audience identified and the messages to be transmitted to maximise impact.
- Section 12 describes the dissemination and communication tools developed within PILOTING project.
- Section 13 sets the KPIs for the evaluation and monitoring of dissemination and communication activities, and also the procedures to record the necessary evidences.
- Section 14 summarizes the main conclusions of the Exploitation and Dissemination Plan.

2. Market size analysis

Before starting to develop the exploitation plan, it is desirable to have an idea of the targeted market size of PILOTING project in the framework of the priority sectors identified in the project: Oil & Gas (refineries) and Civil Inspection (bridges and tunnels of the transport sector).

According to recent market studies, the use of professional robots for inspection and maintenance activities is growing. In fact, some of the PILOTING partners (CATEC, USE and SINTEF) also participate as part of the [RIMA](#) Consortium, H2020 project focused on connecting and inspiring key stakeholders in I&M robotics and aims to accelerate innovation and uptake of robotics between these stakeholders. One of the main outputs of this project has been the elaboration of an exhaustive market study: "Robotic for inspection & maintenance Global market overview".

As part of this consortium, PILOTING partners have closely followed the elaboration of this market study, attending to the follow-up meetings. Therefore, it is necessary to point out that it has a very clear knowledge about it and how this study has served as the main source of information.

RIMA market study has been structured in two phases:

- Phase 1: Global market overview.
 - o Screening of the web to catch market figures within robotics and infrastructures reports, identifying the following:
 - Technavio 2020¹.
 - Persistence Market Research 2019².
 - Shingetsu Research 2020³.

¹ <https://www.technavio.com/report/inspection-robots-market-industry-analysis>

² <https://www.persistencemarketresearch.com/market-research/infrastructure-inspection-robots-market.asp>

³ <https://www.shingetsuresearch.com/inspection-and-maintenance-robot-market/>

- Fortune Business Insights 2020 - Inspection, Repair and Maintenance market⁴.
- IFTR - World Robotics 2018 Service Robots⁵
- Grandview Research 2017 – US professional service robots⁶
- Credence research 2017⁷
- Highlights on some industrial sectors or some infrastructures.
 - Figures shows that oil & gas stands out with 60% of the robotics inspection market and the 1st sector for drones inspection markets, but opportunities exist in many other industries, like transport infrastructures.
 - The main infrastructures identified as relevant are pipelines, oil rigs, jackup & drilling, tanks and vessels, sewer and civil engineering structures.
- Observation / analysis of the value chain.
 - Larger players of the inspection robot market, who are companies positioned on characterization/inspection activities, are acquiring robotic techno providers companies for difficult inspection tasks and also providing maintenance services
 - Playground of inspection players seems to be driven by sensors within the robotic field and vectors within the drone field.
 - Drones, high tech embedded sensors and inspection services have been detected as the keystone for providing a response to infrastructure's inspection & maintenance needs
- Technological issues or requirements
 - Important technological challenges have been identified:
 - So many use cases and services to do: large areas inspection, crack detection, the automated procession of inspection data, etc.
 - Sometimes very strong mobility constraints.
 - A wide range of sensors for various purposes-
 - Embedded capacities.
- Phase 2: Directly from the demand side. Learnings from 30 to 50 use cases related to 7 topics : Oil & gas, Wind farms, Industrial water, Rail, Power lines / electric grid, Underwater infrastructures and planes. This phase has been based on interviews with sectorial experts around key questions:
 - What about robotics for inspection & maintenance?
 - How could you describe the current operations?
 - What's your views on the future?
 - What could be key levers that favour such technologies for inspection & maintenance? And what about hurdles?
 - May we imagine having a market dedicated to this and how could it look like ?

⁴ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/inspection-repair-and-maintenance-market-102983>

⁵ https://ifr.org/downloads/press2018/Executive_Summary_WR_Service_Robots_2018.pdf

⁶ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/professional-service-robots-market>

⁷ <https://www.credenceresearch.com/report/big-data-analytics-market>

Some of the experts who participated in the RIMA market study are: VOPAK, Square Robot, FH Aachen, University of Applied Sciences, Acwa Robotics, Jetty Robot, KWR, Railway robotics, Framatome and Rope robotics.

The answers to these questions showed the interest of the I&M industry, where robots can be used for almost all components. In addition, the game is not just about inspection but also reparation and cleaning.

The figures below have been deduced from this market study.

In 2018 the total sales of professional robots rose by 61% to more than 271,000 units, up from roughly 168,000 in 2017. The sales value of these systems is estimated at almost USD 3.7 billion which is 53% more than the year before. The category of inspection and maintenance robots represent an important fraction in the professional service robot market. About 106,000 inspection and maintenance systems were sold in 2018. This accounts for 39% of total professional service robot units sold. The dynamism of the service robot sector, illustrated by strong growth in 2018, is set to continue. The sales value of professional service robots is estimated to increase by 45% on average per year between 2019 and 2022, reaching a total of about USD 38 billion in 2022⁸.

Moreover, the Technavio Market Research Institute ⁹ forecasted that the global inspection robot market has the potential to grow by USD 3.72 billion during 2020-2024, of which over 38% is expected to be ordered with European companies.

Among the end-user industries, oil and gas industry is the major stakeholder in the growth of inspection robots market followed by chemical industry (with large similarities in inspection and maintenance operations) due to their numerous complex processes and equipment used. Also, civil infrastructure sector has a large potential due to the criticality and high risk operations.

These reported figures by market analyses focus on the manufacturing and sales side of robotics use, but the robotic inspection and maintenance service market is not only related to the robotic equipment sale aspects, but also the added value services that can be offered thanks to the use of the robotic platforms, including advanced data analytics that can be generated thanks to the high quality and large amount of data that can be gathered with robotic platforms. Therefore, the real impact of robotics inspection and maintenance industry is much larger with a potential global market of several billion of euros in the next years. In fact, and just taking into consideration aerial robots, according to the European Drones Outlook Market Study¹⁰ (2016), it is estimated that, by 2035, inspections with aerial robots in infrastructures will generate 1.600M€/year just in Europe.

⁸ World Robotics 2019 Service Robotics International Federation of Robotic (IFR)

⁹ <https://www.technavio.com/report/inspection-robots-market-industry-analysis>

¹⁰ https://www.sesarju.eu/sites/default/files/documents/reports/European_Drones_Outlook_Study_2016.pdf

With respect to PILOTING end-users (Chevron, Ferrovial and Egnatia) a preliminary market estimation has been performed for the three considered scenarios (refineries, bridges/viaducts and tunnels).

Chevron - Refineries	Ferrovial - Viaduct/bridges	Egnatia - Tunnels
Chevron Oronite refinery requires around 50.000 inspection points every 3 years. Assuming 70% of remote measurements, inspector salaries and the costs associated to access, it can be estimated that each refinery spends around 3M€/year in inspection services.	Inspections of viaducts cost is between 3000€-5000€ depending on their sizes, they are carried out once a year, and the average number of viaducts is one viaduct every 50km of railway track. Ferrovial maintains 4050km of railway track in Spain. Then, the potential market for robotic inspection will be $4000€ \times 4050/50 = 324.000 €$ per year.	An average of 3 permanent technicians per km is needed for inspection of tunnels. For Metsovo tunnel this means around 270K€ just in salaries plus all the required equipment to perform the inspections.

Table 2. Preliminary market estimation for the three considered scenarios with respect to PILOTING end-users.

If these numbers are extrapolated to the European Union:

Refineries	Viaduct/bridges	Tunnels
101 refineries are located in Europe which means a potential market of more than 300M€/year.	From Europe's 1.5 million bridges, around 55.000 require continuous inspection due to their criticality or age. Assuming 1/3 can be inspected with robotics technologies, then the potential market is around 70M€/year.	There are 15.000 km of tunnels in Europe. 50% are more than 30 years old, and assuming 1/4 can be inspected with robotics technologies, then the potential market is around 170M€/year

Table 3. Preliminary market estimation for the three considered scenarios with respect to the EU.

As can be seen, even considering three specific cases, the potential economic impact is huge (more than 540M€/year). Even more taking into account that these numbers do not include other not tangible benefits such as risk reduction, increase of competitiveness, and savings due to early identification of damages.

3. Identification of initial Key Exploitable Results (KER)

A first step for developing an appropriate and comprehensive Exploitation Plan is to identify the list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). These KERs will be the base to start the exploitation plan that has the objective to identify the most promising business models (see Section 6) that can be industrialized after the project. This KER list will be evaluated regularly.

The table below (Table 4) summarizes the expected results to be generated through the project, together with a brief description and the main partner identified as responsible for its development.

KER N°	Key Exploitable result	Brief description	Exploited by
KER 1	Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots	This KER will be based on an aerial robot that is able to perform ultrasound contact inspections and obtain wall thickness measurements. Moreover, this aerial robot implements an “inspection” navigation mode where the operator can directly move the inspection sensor while the aerial robot will automatically follow it and maintain the contact with the surface.	CATEC
KER 2	GNSS-free aerial robot navigation in large areas	This KER is about an aerial robot that is able to navigate without the need of GNSS as the primary navigation system in large areas (for example a viaduct or bridge). The aerial robot will also be able to follow pre-defined missions and automatically follow the corresponding flight plans.	CATEC
KER 3	Hybrid robot for pipes inspection in refineries	This KER is based on a hybrid robot that will be able to navigate in complex spaces and land on pipes. Once it is landed, it will be able to perform a complete inspection on complex pipes segments (like elbows and Ts).	CATEC
KER 4	Generic Robot Control Station	This KER is about a generic control station that will be compatible with a large number of robotics systems for I&M. The generic robot control station will be used for planning and supervision of the robotic system and it will facilitate the training of a single operator for different robotics systems.	CATEC
KER 5	Texture-based defect detection and classification	This KER is based on a software module that can segment images and classify large variety of materials and defects. The module consists of a segmentation algorithm and a trained neural network. Using an overview image and only a small number of close-up images, this AI-based	HONEYWELL

		solution can provide deep analysis of the whole photographed area.	
KER 6	Quickly building 3D asset models	This KER is based on AssetBuilder, a webbased tool to create 3D models of assets with detailed CAD experience or tools. For robotic navigation and data presentation, 3D models are often required, but not available. Quasset is developing AssetBuilder to allow users to create 3D asset models, using parametrized parts, e.g. for manway, shell, heads, nozzles etc. AssetBuilder will support multiple asset types.	QUASSET
KER 7	Inspection data overlay on 3D assets	This KER will be based on robotic inspection data presentation module. This module offers an easily interpretable way of presenting robotic inspection data on 3D models of assets. This module supports different inspection data types and various 3D file formats. It is web-based.	QUASSET
KER 8	Asset annotation of key inspection data	This KER will be based on Asset annotation module called Asset Annotator which offers a clean and easy method to make annotations on 3D asset models quickly and easily.	QUASSET
KER 9	AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks	This KER will be based on a set of AI-based applications that ICCS will develop that will be able to discriminate between Inspection Images that represent healthy samples of infrastructure points with those that represent defects as well as to classify the type of defect observed. The former will be based on Novelty detection algorithms that will be able to assist the manual annotation process of inspection data, while the latter will be based on advanced deep learning methods that will allow the automatic annotation of inspection images regarding the types of defects.	ICCS
KER 10	Data Management System	This KER will be based on a set of data storage, distribution and harmonization services and solutions that will comprise the PILOTING Data Management System and Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer. The integrated solution will be able to collect heterogeneous data (incl. inspection images and videos, on-robot sensor readings, detailed inspection task definition) from a Robot Control Station and from Sensor Systems (incl. Legacy Systems of the Infrastructure and IoT Sensors), harmonize them using specified data-models and store them using a distributed storage solution with time and location indexing	ICCS

		capabilities. Additionally, the system will be able to provide services in order for a visualization portal to be able to retrieve data and also to define a Mission definition that will be forwarded to a Robot Control Station in order to be specialized to specific tasks. Finally, the System will be able to interact with external services (e.g. AI-based image analysis tools) by providing data retrieval and metadata (image analysis results) management services.	
KER 11	Mission Planning Interface	Exclusively humans using joystick controls currently control the GEIR crawler robots. Missions are planned mostly on paper and executed manually. A key element for standardized inspections using robots is standardizing on the mission planning and execution. Within the PILOTING project, a standardized interface for submitting a mission plan to a GEIR crawler will be developed. This interface will enable the GEIR robots to accept mission plans from different end-users by providing them with a standard input format. The economic impact from this KER will be based on the fact that asset-owners can standardize on inspection plans in digital format and execute them using GEIR robots.	GEIR
KER 12	Mission Execution by Waypoint Navigation	A mission for inspection using surface adhering crawlers consists of a sequence of waypoints. Such waypoints may be inspection locations (points of interests) or waypoints required for successful mission execution (i.e. points required for obstacle passing). One task within the PILOTING project is to enable the surface adhering inspection robots to move from one waypoint to another without the need of operator interaction. Given the waypoint navigation, execution of entire missions based on a sequence of waypoints becomes feasible.	GEIR
KER 13	Installation of surveying targets by aerial robots	This KER consists of an aerial robot that is able to install surveying targets on bridges or viaducts. These targets are small devices that can be used later to improve the accuracy of visual inspections (i.e. having a ruler) or to take geometric measurements of the structure with a total station (i.e. with a reflective part). This is achieved by being in contact with the viaduct's structure. The	USE

		aerial robot can perform this installation autonomously or in assisted mode.	
KER 14	Tunnel close visual inspection by aerial robots	This KER consists of an aerial robot that is able to perform visual inspections inside of a tunnel. This implies solving the aerodynamic and localization problems in such a narrow and constrained environment as a tunnel. It will be achieved through robust control techniques and SLAM algorithms. In addition, this robot could be equipped with a lighting system to be able to take close images of the infrastructure with enough quality.	USE
KER 15	Stable contact and crawling by aerial robots	This KER consists of an aerial robot that is able to stick itself to an upper horizontal surface (e.g. a viaduct's deck) and move through the surface without losing contact. This ability allows the aerial robot to reach inaccessible places (e.g. close to the bearings of a viaduct) and to gain stability to take more accurate measurements or images. In addition, an external total station can take very accurate measurements of the deflection of a bridge or viaduct.	USE
KER 16	PILOTING I&M platform	This Key Exploitable Result will be based on one of the core outcomes of the project, the PILOTING Inspection and Maintenance Platform (I&M platform) which comprises of the following key parts of the solution: the Robot Control Station, the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer as well as the Data Management System. The exploitation aim of the I&M platform is to be offered to end-users primarily in the transport and oil and gas industries and others to perform overall maintenance tasks of infrastructures during their whole lifetime, preventing accidents and fulfilling the required regulations and industrial standards. The PILOTING I&M platform will be designed following a scalable and open architecture in order to facilitate the integration of different types of robotic systems into new business cases related to inspection and maintenance.	INLECOM
KER 17	Data Distribution and Harmonization component	This Key Exploitable Result will be based on the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization component, which will be developed as a part of I&M platform by INLECOM. This is a vector-specific data ingestion component for IoT systems. It is related to the connectivity between	INLECOM

		I&M platform parts (including Robot Control Station, IoT Sensors and Data Management System), to the data transformation to robotics-related data models as well as to the data distribution through Middleware interfaces.	
KER 18	Overall tunnel inspection robot	This robot will be based on the automation of an electric cart, performed on a 4 wheeled vehicle which will be prepared for autonomous operations. Its carrying capacity will be increased; including the installation of an elevation crane to position the sensor loads (several types of cameras and LIDARs) up to 3 meter high. This robot will also incorporate a special platform for aerial robot take-off and landing. Special effort will be put for developing protocols and including the hardware that will provide a safe operation of the solution.	RBNK
KER 19	Refinery inspection and maintenance robot	This robot will be based on an existing vehicle from Robotnik which consists on a mobile manipulator specially designed for intervention, reconnaissance and inspection missions, able to mount specific sensors and with a high mobility kinematic configuration that allows accessing adverse and rough terrains and stair climbing.	RBNK
KER 20	Mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception	This KER will allow a mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception to detect and avoid any unexpected obstacles. Navigation is based on a simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) system that has been specialized for areas with very sparse visual and structural features.	SINTEF
KER 21	Localization and Mapping System in Refineries	This KER is the specialization of a localization and mapping system towards the challenging refinery scenario. The developed system will be able to map and localize by being teleoperated on a first mission or on autonomous navigation mode one a prior map is available. The main characteristics of this system is its robustness to the challenging perception posed by the infrastructure and the environment, and it high accuracy.	ETHZ

Table 4. PILOTING Exploitable RESULTS.

4. Initial analysis of key exploitable results

In this section we further analyse all the exploitable results that were presented in the previous section.

4.1 KER 1: Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots

	KER 1
Innovation introduced	Aerial robot that is able to maintain contact while flying in a robust way. Also, it is able to offer an “inspection” navigation mode that facilitates the inspection procedure.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The aerial robotic system has to comply with the new European Drone regulation, and also with the requirements imposed by refineries specially the ones related to explosive atmosphere aspects.
Competitors	There are a few companies that have just started to commercialize contact inspection solutions with drones (like for example Voliro and Ronik).
Current TRL	Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by CATEC. Contact system patented by CATEC.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by CATEC at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	It is foreseen two types of products/services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerial robotic system as a tool that can be sold to inspection service providers. • Direct service provision of wall thickness measurements that can be provided directly to assets owners.

Table 5. KER 1: Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots.

4.2 KER 2: GNSS-free aerial robot navigation in large areas

	KER 2
Innovation introduced	GNSS-free navigation for aerial robots that allows performing waypoint navigation in large areas with degraded GNSS coverage.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The aerial robotic system or subsystem has to comply with the new European Drone regulation, and also with the requirements imposed by the infrastructure managers.
Competitors	There is not any drone on the market that can perform completely automatic GNSS-free waypoint navigation. The only product, that we are aware and could be used for this purpose, is Hovermap by Emesent. However, it seems more oriented to 3D mapping although the specifications says that it could be used for GNSS-free navigation of DJI drones.

Current TRL	Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by CATEC.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by CATEC at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	It is foreseen two types of products: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigation subsystem to be integrated in third party drones. • Aerial robotic system as a tool that can be sold to inspection service providers.

Table 6. KER 2: GNSS-free aerial robot in large areas

4.3 KER 3: Hybrid robot for pipes inspection in refineries

	KER 3
Innovation introduced	Hybrid robot with a novel configuration that allows performing a complete pipe segment inspection after the robot is landed on it. The fact that the inspection is performed after landing allows to save energy and be able to inspect a larger number of pipes, and also, a
SoEL barriers or requirements	The aerial robotic system has to comply with the new European Drone regulation, and also with the requirements imposed by refineries specially the ones related to explosive atmosphere aspects.
Competitors	We are not aware of any similar product or technological development. The only possible competitors are crawlers, but they are usually wired. And then, much more limited with respect to the capability to reach complex locations.
Current TRL	Technology validated in the laboratory (TRL 4)
Status of background IPR	Technology is owned by CATEC (aerial robot) and GEIR (satellite robot with inspection probe).
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by CATEC and GEIR (respectively) at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	It is foreseen two types of products: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hybrid robotic system as a tool that can be sold to inspection service providers. • Direct service provision of wall thickness measurements that can be provided directly to assets owners.

Table 7. KER 3: Hybrid robot for pipes inspection in refineries.

4.4 KER 4: Generic Robot Control Station

	KER 4
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Innovation introduced	A common robot control station that can be used for both ground and aerial robots.
SoEL barriers or requirements	None
Competitors	As far as we are aware there is not any robot control station software that can be used for both ground and aerial robots, and even more, it we are considering specifically inspection operations.
Current TRL	Technology validated in the laboratory (TRL 4)
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by CATEC
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by CATEC
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	It is foreseen two types of products/services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This software can be sold as a module for inspection robotics systems to inspection service providers. • This software can be sold to robot manufacturers to be integrated, and personalized, for their robotic systems.

Table 8. KER 4: Generic Robot Control Station.

4.5 KER 5: Texture-based defect detection and classification

	KER 5
Innovation introduced	A neural network designed for material defect recognition. The network can be relatively easily adapted for new material/failure combination annotated by an expert in material engineering.
SoEL barriers or requirements	None
Competitors	Although there are companies that offer automated/intelligent inspection based on images, none of them is using this novel texture based NN algorithm so we think this will be a differential factor in creating an added value product.
Current TRL	Experimental proof of concept (TRL 3)
Status of background IPR	Annotation techniques and tool; crack detection; basic corrosion detection
Planned status of foreground IPR	Steel corrosion and coating failure, concrete defects (delamination, rebars exposure, crack detection), watering sediments detection
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	The product is foreseen to be part of a complex automated solution consisting of robots taking high resolution images and a user portal for obtaining the results. The target customers are infrastructure maintainers as well as inspection & maintenance service providers.

Table 9. KER 5: Texture-based defect detection and classification.

4.6 KER 6: Quickly building 3D asset models

	KER 6
Innovation introduced	AssetBuilder introduces an easy to use way create 3D asset models, build using part libraries. The resulting models can be used for robotic simulation, navigation and data visualization.
SoEL barriers or requirements	None
Competitors	We are not aware of similar projects/products in the PILOTING application domains
Current TRL	Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by QUASSET.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by QUASSET at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	It is foreseen two types of products/services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This module can be sold as a module for an inspection robotics portal to robot manufacturers and inspection service providers. • This module can be sold as SaaS separately to end users and inspection service providers.

Table 10. KER 6: Quickly building 3D asset models.

4.7 KER 7: Inspection data overlay on 3D assets

	KER 7
Innovation introduced	Robotic inspection 3D data presentation module introduces an easy to use way visualizing and reporting inspection data on the 3D asset model. Together with the asset annotator this module offers a seamless visual solution to evaluate and interpret the whole inspection plan executed on the asset as well recording the findings.
SoEL barriers or requirements	None
Competitors	There exists proprietary solution developed by and for specific robotic solutions. These have limited reach and cannot be used to create holistic overview of inspection data gathered from a variety of robotic inspection solution
Current TRL	Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by QUASSET.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by QUASSET at the end of PILOTING project.

<p>Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers</p>	<p>It is foreseen two types of products/services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This module can be sold as a module for an inspection robotics portal to robot manufacturers and inspection service providers. • This module can be sold as SaaS separately to end users and inspection service providers.
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Table 11. KER 7: Inspection data overlay on 3D assets.

4.8 KER 8: Asset annotation of key inspection data

	KER 8
<p>Innovation introduced</p>	<p>Asset Annotator introduces an intuitive way of creating annotations on the 3D model of your asset. It is web based and works on various browsers. It supports various 3D file formats. Image annotations and 3D asset annotations can be mapped. Annotations in the context of a 3D model help navigating to location related asset and inspection data.</p>
<p>SoEL barriers or requirements</p>	<p>none</p>
<p>Competitors</p>	<p>Similar functionalities exist in the context of BIM suites, but these have not found their way into inspection and maintenance field.</p>
<p>Current TRL</p>	<p>Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)</p>
<p>Status of background IPR</p>	<p>Technology owned by QUASSET.</p>
<p>Planned status of foreground IPR</p>	<p>It is planned that this technology will still be owned by QUASSET at the end of PILOTING project.</p>
<p>Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers</p>	<p>It is foreseen two types of products/services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This module can be sold as an optional module for an inspection robotics portal to robot manufacturers and inspection service providers. • This module can be sold as SaaS separately to end users and inspection service providers.

Table 12. KER 8: Asset annotation of key inspection data.

4.9 KER 9: AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks

	KER 9
<p>Innovation introduced</p>	<p>The AI-based applications to be developed will introduce an innovative framework for analysing inspection images in order to significantly support the manual annotation process for inspection images as well to offer a mechanism for automatically detecting and identifying/classifying defects in Inspection images with a capability of processing big number of images in short time. Compared to the existing solutions, the developed applications will not require a</p>

	precise segmentation of defects for the data consisting the training set and will also be able to discriminate between images that include or not include defects before classifying the former to different categories, therefore will not require any filtering of newly captured data.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The inspection images should of high quality (at least 3-4 pixels per feature width) as well as representing 2D-surfaces.
Competitors	There are several competitors in the field including Canon focusing on detecting cracks with AI technology, Inspection2 that offers a solution for asset inspection using AI, Dynamic Infrastructure that tracks defects in bridges and tunnels in order to provide maintenance alerts and AiviewGroup that offers an AI-inspection API that catalogues, manages and analyses data from assets.
Current TRL	Technology Validated in the laboratory (TRL 4)
Status of background IPR	Technology developed and implemented by ICCS using several open-source tools and AI algorithms
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by ICCS at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	The foreseen product will consist of a set of AI-based applications for assisting the analysis of Inspection Images in terms of supporting their manual annotation and of automatically identifying/classifying defects.

Table 13. KER 9: AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks.

4.10 KER 10: Data Management System

	KER 10
Innovation introduced	The Data Management System and its Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer will offer an integrated solution for Inspection and Maintenance data handling including the management of authentication and authorization for accessing and processing data as well as defining and handling Mission Definitions. The system will be designed and implemented in a way to offer innovative solutions in terms of multi-modal indexing of heterogeneous data, unifying different standards in a uniform and transparent way and seamless support of multiple data formats.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The systems to be integrated should comply with widely accepted and used open standards for services related to data exchange.
Competitors	Several companies in the private sector have developed solutions for Inspection and Maintenance data handling (Clearion, Assetedge, Intertek). Additionally there are several initiatives in the Research field mainly from United States (University of Stanford and Michigan) and Asia (Korea Advance Institute of Science and Technology).
Current TRL	Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)

Status of background IPR	Technology developed and implemented by ICCS using several open-source tools and specifications.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by ICCS at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	The foreseen product will consist of a data management solution for Inspection and Maintenance procedures that will allow the integration of heterogeneous robotic platforms as well as visualization and inspection data analysis services.

Table 14. KER 10: AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks.

4.11 KER 11: Mission Planning Interface

	KER 11
Innovation introduced	Standardized mission-planning interface for surface adhering inspection robots.
SoEL barriers or requirements	Not applicable
Competitors	The main competition is currently still manual inspection carried out by humans entering confined spaces. Some competition comes from collision tolerant drones developing contact inspection capabilities. In the segment of surface adhering crawling robots only, very few systems are available and currently none of them can work based on a standardized mission plan.
Current TRL	Technology validated in relevant environment (TRL 5)
Status of background IPR	GEIR has used this concept in the past for different types of inspection devices, but never so far for surface adhering robots moving in three-dimensional space.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that the this technology will be owned by GEIR at the end of PILOTING project
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	Inspection system based on surface adhering inspection robots with the capability of integration with a standardized repeatable digital inspection process (mission plan) provided by asset owners.

Table 15. KER 11: Mission Planning Interface.

4.12 KER 12: Mission Execution by Waypoint Navigation

	KER 12
Innovation introduced	Waypoint based navigation of surface adhering inspection robots.
SoEL barriers or requirements	Not applicable

Competitors	The main competition is currently still manual inspection carried out by humans entering confined spaces. Some competition comes from collision tolerant drones developing contact inspection capabilities. In the segment of surface adhering crawling robots only, very few systems are available and currently none of them can execute missions without operator interaction.
Current TRL	Technology validated in lab (TRL 4)
Status of background IPR	GEIR has successfully implemented waypoint navigation for two-dimensional robot navigation. The generalization for three dimensions however was never attempted.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that the this technology will be owned by GEIR at the end of PILOTING project
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	Inspection system based on surface adhering inspection robots with the capability of mission execution without operator interaction. This is regarded by the industry as a key element to achieving truly repeatable inspections.

Table 16. KER 12: Mission Execution by Waypoint Navigation.

4.13 KER 13: Installation of surveying targets by aerial robots

	KER 13
Innovation introduced	Aerial robot that is able to physically interact with the structure and install a small device.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The aerial robotic system has to comply with the new European Drone regulation and with safety concerns related to the possible traffic on top of the bridge or viaduct.
Competitors	There are only few companies that are commercializing contact inspection solutions with drones, but not giving this specific solution at the moment.
Current TRL	Technology partially demonstrated in the lab and in controlled environments (TRL 4-5).
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by the University of Seville.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by the University of Seville at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	Two types of products/services are foreseen: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerial robotic system as a tool that can be sold to inspection service providers. • Direct service provision of device installation that can be provided directly to assets owners.

Table 17. KER 13: Installation of surveying targets by aerial robots.

4.14 KER 14: Tunnel close visual inspection by aerial robots

	KER 14
Innovation introduced	Aerial robot that is able to take high quality images for visual inspection from a very close distance to the defects.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The aerial robotic system has to comply with safety concerns related to the possible traffic inside the tunnel. Moreover, the system should reliably work inside a possibly dark and narrow environment.
Competitors	There are only few companies that are commercializing visual inspection solutions with drones, but not giving this specific solution in this kind of environments at the moment.
Current TRL	Technology partially demonstrated in the lab and in controlled environments (TRL 4-5).
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by the University of Seville.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by the University of Seville at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	Two types of products/services are foreseen: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerial robotic system as a tool that can be sold to inspection service providers. • Direct service provision of visual inspection in tunnels that can be provided directly to assets owners.

Table 18. KER 14: Tunnel close visual inspection by aerial robots.

4.15 KER 15: Stable contact and crawling by aerial robots

	KER 15
Innovation introduced	Aerial robot that is able to stick to an upper horizontal surface, maintaining contact and ensuring a stable position, and then is able to move through this surface without losing contact.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The aerial robotic system has to comply with the new European Drone regulation and with safety concerns related to the possible traffic on top of the bridge or viaduct.
Competitors	There are only few companies that are commercializing contact inspection solutions with drones, but not giving this specific solution at the moment.
Current TRL	Technology partially demonstrated in the lab, in controlled environments and in relevant environments (TRL 4-6).
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by the University of Seville.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will still be owned by the University of Seville at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	It is foreseen three types of products/services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerial robotic system as a tool that can be sold to inspection service providers.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct service provision of deflection measurements that can be provided directly to assets owners. • Direct service provision of visual inspection of inaccessible areas that can be provided directly to assets owners.
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Table 19. KER 15: Stable contact and crawling by aerial robots

4.16 KER 16: PILOTING I&M platform

	KER 16
Innovation introduced	The PILOTING I&M platform introduces a one of a kind integrated and unified system that targets the inspection industry by orchestrating heterogeneous state-of-the-art technologies and services in a robotic-agnostic approach providing connectivity, data integration, robotics control, and data management.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The PILOTING I&M platform will comply with the cybersecurity and safety regulation and standards.
Competitors	There are only a few companies that have just started to commercialize inspection platform solutions for robotics (such as GE).
Current TRL	Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)
Status of background IPR	Technology developed and implemented by CATEC (Robot Control Station), INLECOM (I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer) and ICCS (Data Management System).
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that the developed platform will be owned under a shared scheme by CATEC, INLECOM and ICCS, based on the separately developed components.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	As a first step, the integrated I&M platform will be exploited to three specific sectors (refineries, bridges/viaducts, and tunnels), based on the use case scenarios of the project. Potential target customers could be civil infrastructure sector companies, transport infrastructure operators as well as refineries operator, taking into account that 1.5 million bridges, 15.000 km of tunnels and 101 refineries are located in Europe.

Table 20. KER 16: PILOTING I&M platform

4.17 KER 17: I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization component

	KER 17
Innovation introduced	The I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization component introduce a novel and powerful network management system allowing the connectivity of heterogeneous systems (robotic controls station, IoT sensors, cloud-based data management system) and the data distribution under a common language (unified data models for I&M robotics).

SoEL barriers or requirements	The PILOTING Data Distribution and Harmonization will comply with existing cybersecurity and safety regulations and standards.
Competitors	Data Ingestion Systems for IoT systems are commonly available by many providers in various formats (e.g. PaaS). Although, there is not currently available any system that is dedicated to the I&M robotics.
Current TRL	Technology demonstrated in relevant environments (TRL 6)
Status of background IPR	INLECOM has already available common products (such as NMS system for IoT networks). The technology developed and implemented by INLECOM will be based on them.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that the developed service will be owned by INLECOM.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	The foreseen service will be exploited to several sectors such as Remote Monitoring IoT Systems, ICT, Industrial Control Systems (ICS), SCADA, and similar industrial sectors.

Table 21. KER 17: &M Data Distribution and Harmonization component

4.18 KER 18: Overall tunnel inspection robot

	KER 18
Innovation introduced	Improvement of non-GNSS safe navigation at high speed. Upgraded autonomous detection of defects based on AI Accurate 3D modelling using LIDAR-based technologies. Fast and safe deployment and usage of the solution.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The robot must comply with the requirements stated by the highway end-user. The trials will be made under specific conditions and respecting mitigation actions for not to disturb the normal functioning of the critical infrastructure.
Competitors	N.A
Current TRL	High TRL. Next to 7
Status of background IPR	The robot is based on an existing robotic platform which is 100% owned by Robotnik
Planned status of foreground IPR	Ideally the final robot developed within PILOTING will be owned by Robotnik.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	The foreseen product is a marketable robot able to autonomously perform tunnel inspections, addressed to companies dealing with the design, construction, supervision, operation or maintenance of roads.

Table 22. KER 18: Overall tunnel inspection robot

4.19 KER 19: Refinery inspection&maintenance robot

	KER 19
Innovation introduced	Improvements on complex spaces navigation, enhancement of climbing capabilities. Development of new detection capabilities (detection of sound alarms and pump gauges read, etc.). Upgraded dexterous manipulation of actuators
SoEL barriers or requirements	The robot should adhere to the safety requirements stated by the refinery end-user. An specific risk-assessment must be made for trials and demonstrations on-site.
Competitors	Packbot robot, Talon robot
Current TRL	High TRL. Next to 7
Status of background IPR	The robot is based on an existing robotic platform which is 100% owned by Robotnik
Planned status of foreground IPR	Ideally the final robot developed within PILOTING will be owned by Robotnik.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	The foreseen product is a marketable robot able to autonomously perform inspection and some easy maintenance activities in gas and oil related industries.

Table 23. KER 19: Refinery inspection&maintenance robot

4.20 KER 20: Mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception

	KER 20
Innovation introduced	Localization in a GNSS-denied environment with sparse visual and structural features.
SoEL barriers or requirements	The mobile platform needs to comply with relevant safety standards for autonomous vehicles.
Competitors	The main competition is manually driven vehicles.
Current TRL	TRL 2
Status of background IPR	We are not intending to base solution on protected background IPR.
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned that this technology will be owned by SINTEF at the end of the PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	The solution is intended to be commercialized as a module for robot systems. The target customers include autonomous vehicle manufacturers in areas such as I&M and search and rescue. It may also be included as background IP for future research projects.

Table 24. KER 20: Mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception.

4.21 KER 21: Localization and Mapping System in Refineries

	KER 21
Innovation introduced	Robust and precise localization and mapping system for autonomous robotic navigation in outdoor and GNSS-degraded industrial infrastructure (e.g., gas&oil refineries).
SoEL barriers or requirements	None
Competitors	Unaware
Current TRL	The localization and mapping system has been validated in other difficult environments with different challenges (tunnels/mines/search and rescue/indoor industrial plants). TRL 6.
Status of background IPR	Technology owned by ETHZ
Planned status of foreground IPR	It is planned the technology will still be owned by ETHZ at the end of PILOTING project.
Foreseen Product/Service including Target Customers	It is foreseen the product will be the software stack to be deployed in a ground robot navigation pipeline. Target customers are companies providing robotic technologies for inspection and maintenance.

Table 25. KER 21: Localization and Mapping System in Refineries.

5. Exploitation tools

PILOTING consortium has developed an initial set of tools to ensure an effective identification of technologies and services that could be exploited after the project, and also, to support the matching and adaptation of these technologies and services to end-user needs. These tools are described in the section below.

5.1 Early identification of exploitation opportunities

PILOTING consortium has agreed to present exploitation opportunities at the Steering Committee meetings, to get early feedback on viability and commercial value of proposed solutions. Opportunities will be evaluated in terms of business readiness level (i.e., the degree of readiness a business sector is to adopt new solutions), technological readiness level, as well as a level of impact (e.g., in terms of economic benefit, reduced environmental footprint, etc.).

The first list of exploitation opportunities will be based on the list of KER (already presented in Section 4).

5.2 Organization of PILOTING workshops

On the other hand, PILOTING will organize three workshops during the project. With respect to exploitation aspects, the workshops will consider:

- The first one (M6) will be used to present PILOTING use cases and get feedback about the interest of the I&M sector in those use cases.
- The second one will include a public innovation session (M32) for connecting technology and service providers with potential end-users, both within and outside the project consortium. The main objective of this innovation session will be to validate the identified value propositions with a larger number of end-users. The value propositions make reference to the product and/or services that PILOTING offers in order to meet the needs of its customers. The most interesting value propositions will be used to further develop a complete business plan.
- The last one (M46) will be used to further developed the final business plans and get feedback about them.

PILOTING workshops will be mainly oriented to I&M industrial actors (system/robotics developers, service inspection companies and end-users). Then, the PILOTING User group will be essential to disseminate and attract enough attention to these workshops.

The workshops will also include slots for discussion and interaction with the audience. As an example of the organization of the workshops, below can be found some details about the first PILOTING workshop organized by PILOTING on June 25th:

- Agenda:
 - 10:00-10:05 Foreword by EC
 - 10:05-10:15 PILOTING project introduction
 - 10:15-11:00 PILOTING use cases and identified requirements
 - 11:00-11:30 PILOTING functional specifications
 - 11:30-12:00 Feedback from stakeholders
 - 12:00-12:45 Presentation of H2020 projects related with I&M (RIMA DIH, ATLANTIS, METRICS and AERIAL-CORE)
 - 12:45-13:00 Conclusions of the workshop
- Audience statistics:
 - 180 people registered.
 - 104 people attended to the workshop from 26 different countries (18 European and 8 outside Europe: USA, Mexico, Canada, Japan, Brazil, Saudi Arabia, Singapore and Turkey).
 - More than 50% of the attendants come from industry.
- Due to the covid-19 situation, the workshop was held as a webinar using Livestorm tool (<https://livestorm.co/>), see Figure 1.

Figure 1. The first PILOTING workshop on June 25th held as a webinar

5.3 Value propositions

Modern value propositions design techniques will be followed within PILOTING to evaluate each of the identified exploitation opportunities. The purpose of this section is to present the techniques best suited to project partners, which are based on the Value Proposition Canvas Model¹¹.

The Value Proposition Canvas is a tool of visual representation that helps to visualise, design and test how you create value for the customers. It is composed of two building blocks: customer profiles and value maps. Figure 2 shows the Value Propositions Canvas template.

Figure 2. Value Propositions Canvas Template.

Customer profile. A customer profile should be created for each customer segment. The objective is to know his needs, problems and behaviours. This block tries to identify:

¹¹ <https://www.b2binternational.com/research/methods/faq/what-is-the-value-proposition-canvas/>

- Gains – the benefits which the customer expects and needs, what would delight customers and the things which may increase likelihood of adopting a value proposition.
- Pains – the negative experiences, emotions and risks that the customer experiences in the process of getting the job done.
- Customer jobs – the functional, social and emotional tasks customers are trying to perform, problems they are trying to solve and needs they wish to satisfy.

Value map. This block defines which element of our value proposition will cover gains, pains and customer jobs.

- Gain creators – how the product or service creates customer gains and how it offers added value to the customer.
- Pain relievers – a description of exactly how the product or service alleviates customer pains.
- Products and services – the products and services which create gain and relieve pain, and which underpin the creation of value for the customer.

By using the Value Proposition Canvas, it is possible to identify customer needs, and come up with products and services to meet those needs, in a visual and structured way. The objective is to come up with products and services that address the most significant pains and gains from the customer profile.

Identifying the value proposition on paper is only the first stage. It is then necessary to validate what is important to customers and get their feedback on the value proposition. These insights can then be used to go back and refine the proposition (see next Section for more details).

5.4 Pilot demonstrations

The execution of pilot demonstrations will be a great tool to confirm that value propositions and also to acquire more information on the “field” before developing a complete business model that will be essential for future exploitation.

Moreover, during pilot demonstrations it will be promoted the organization of interviews with different actors that work at different levels of the end-user organization (inspectors, managers, etc.). These interviews will be really useful to complement the different value propositions, and also to confirm the assumed assumptions. Also, this information will be also used for the development of the business model canvas.

Finally, the pilot demonstrations will also involve participants from outside the consortium to complement the feedback received from the pilot demonstrations.

5.5 Business Model Canvas

Once the most promising value propositions are identified, a business model will be generated for each one using the well-known Business Model Canvas¹².

This business model canvas is used to different prototype concepts of business considering all the key factors: customer segments, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, resources, partnerships, etc. All the elements included in Business Model Canvas can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Elements of Business Model Canvas.

A business model that follows the Business Model Canvas approach must provide information on the following elements:

- **Customer Segments.** To build an effective business model, an organization must identify which customers it tries to serve. Various sets of customers can be segmented based on the different needs and attributes to ensure appropriate implementation of corporate strategy meets the characteristics of selected group of clients.
- **Value Propositions.** The products and/or services the organization offers in order to meet the needs of its customers. A company's value proposition is what distinguishes itself from its competitors.

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business_Model_Canvas

- **Channels.** An organization can deliver its value proposition to its customers through different channels. Effective channels will distribute the value proposition in ways that are fast, efficient and cost effective.
- **Customer Relationships.** To ensure the survival and success of any business, organization must identify the type of relationship they want to create with their customer segments. For example, the way a customer interacts with the organization through the sales and product lifecycle.
- **Revenue Streams.** The way the organization makes income from each customer segment. For example, subscription fees or licensing, etc.
- **Key Activities.** The most important activities in executing the organization's value proposition. For example, for a product-driven business, this includes on-going learning about new techniques to build better product.
- **Key Resources.** The resources that are necessary to create value for the customer. They are considered assets to a company, which are needed in order to sustain and support the business. These resources could be human, financial, physical and intellectual.
- **Key Partnerships.** In order to optimize operations and reduce risks of a business model, organizations usually cultivate buyer-supplier relationships so they can focus on their core activity. Complementary business alliances also can be considered through joint ventures, strategic alliances between competitors or non-competitors.
- **Cost Structure.** This describes the most important monetary consequences while operating under different business models. For example, how do the Key Activities drive the costs.

5.6 Participation in I&M events

PILOTING consortium will participate in I&M events during the lifetime of the project. Participation in such events will allow interacting with stakeholders (including potential end-users), and therefore, it would be a great opportunity to confirm the different assumptions that are considered in the refinement of both the value propositions and business models.

A list of potential I&M events can be found in Section 12.2.4.

5.7 SoEL impact assessment

PILOTING SoEL impact assessment in WP9 will be really useful to have identified the possible societal, ethical and legal barriers that the value propositions and business cases will encounter. This work will be an important input in the identification of the most promising value propositions and business models since it is an important aspect that can generate important barriers in the development of the use cases.

5.8 Participation in standardization groups

The participation in standardization groups will be impact the favour the exploitation of technologies in the following ways:

- Identification of standards currently adopted by industry that can be used in PILOTING technological developments and will facilitate the industrialization of the future products or services.
- If needed, promotion of PILOTING developments or designs as future standards to be adopted by the industry.

Right now, PILOTING partners have active participation in the following standardization bodies: EUROCAE, AIOTI, AIP, IEC and OGC.

5.9 IP management

The management of IP in the project will support the exploitation of project results with effective protection and use of intellectual property. To support the generation of IPR the first steps are to identify and evaluate opportunities where the results of the project work can be protected, for example through patent applications. To a large extent this will be handled by the participants and the partner companies that generate the IPR. However, the project has an important role to help in:

- identification of IPR opportunities
- evaluation of IPR value and proposal of strategy
- coordination of the IPR and dissemination processes.

The WP leaders will continuously monitor progress and identify results which have value as IPR within each WP, and make sure that these are handled with the right level of confidentiality and get evaluated for possible IPR protection.

The potential value of IPR depends on the relevance for standards, industrial application and exploitation strategy. Evaluation of the value will be supported by the steering committee and the IDEM, and strategies for protection and exploitation developed accordingly. The project will produce an open platform (PILOTING I&M Platform) that will contribute to future standards, it is therefore important to consider the right balance between protection and openness, and the best approach to licensing of IPR for the business model.

The procedure for dissemination described in Section 7.1.1 will be followed in order to avoid that results that can be protected are disseminated prematurely. The risk that dissemination will interfere with IPR protection can thereby be monitored by all partners, and dissemination can be postponed or limited such that the necessary protection can be obtained.

The IPR generated within the project will be reported to the consortium and tracked in an IPR directory to keep all partners updated on the status. By keeping tight monitoring of the IPR the project will also help partners to coordinate in order to avoid that, for example, patent filings are interfering with each other by creating prior art.

6. Exploitation Plan

In this section, it will be explained the Exploitation Plan that will be adopted within PILOTING project and should be followed by all partners during the entire duration of the project to finally ensure the achievement of the demanding exploitation goals set by the consortium.

The main objective of the Exploitation Plan is to maximize the probability that certain developments and technologies continue their development and even start an industrialization process after the end of the project. Therefore, the best way to fulfil this objective is to design a plan that allows alignment as much as possible project developments with end-users interests and needs. For this reason, it is important to start with a broad number of options (KER list) and have continuous interaction with a heterogeneous group of stakeholders in order to get their feedback and understand as best as possible their needs and requirements in order to select and further develop, in an iterative way, the most promising business opportunities. Then, PILOTING Exploitation Plan has been defined, having in mind this objective and with the agreement of all consortium partners.

The PILOTING Exploitation Plan consists in the following phases:

1. **Update KER list (M7-M18):** during the design of PILOTING system and the first iteration of technology development, the initial KER list (presented in Section 4) will be updated. The main reason is that during the design and development of PILOTING technologies, partners will have more detailed information and new KERs could be identified.
2. **Identification of most promising value propositions from initial KER (M19-M26):** the second phase of the PILOTING Exploitation Plan is the evaluation of each of the KER identified by the PILOTING consortium and the selection of the most promising ones. First step is to use a value proposition canvas model (see Section 5.3) with the objective to analyse different ways that a KER can be transformed into a product/service that it is useful to end-users. Then, these value propositions will also be analysed taken into account SoEL impact assessment aspects developed in WP9. Next, value propositions will also be analysed from their market size and business impact. As a final step, at least six value propositions will be selected to continue the process.
3. **Confirmation of value propositions (M27-M34):** once the most promising value propositions are selected (at least 6), the plan is to confirm the assumptions taking advantage of different exploitation tools defined in Section 5.
First, and as commented earlier, interviews with different workers at different positions of the end-user organization will be promoted during the first pilot experiments, in order to get a complete understanding of the end-user gains and pains, and refine the value propositions. Also an end-user workshop and Innovation session will be organized in M32 to confirm the value propositions assumptions with a larger number of key stakeholders (from PILOTING User Group).

On the other hand, during the participation in I&M events during this phase, it will be promoted the interaction with potential end-users to also confirm value propositions assumptions.

Finally, the different value propositions will be again analysed and at least three value propositions will be selected for next phase.

4. **Development and confirmation of business models (M35-M46):** once the most promising value propositions are identified and confirmed (at least three), business models will be generated for each one using the well-known business model canvases (defined in Section 5.4). The use of the business model canvas will allow to analyse different business models for the same value proposition and select the most interesting ones. In this case, we will not focus only on the value propositions aspects but also on the complete business model part (cost, revenues, key resources, etc.).

As it happened with the value propositions, the plan is to also use the following exploitation tools to confirm business model assumptions: pilot demonstrations, attendance to I&M events and organization of a workshop (M46). Also, business models will be analysed, taken into account SoEL impact assessment aspects developed in WP9.

Finally, the most interesting business models (at least three) will be further developed with an industrialization plan.

5. **Industrialization plan after the project ends (M46-M48):** at the last phase, an industrialization plan, that will define the steps to be followed to reach the market within 2 years after the end of the project, will be developed. See Section 6.3 for an initial roadmap for this industrialization.

6.1 Individual exploitation plans

One of the most important characteristics of the PILOTING project is that it includes, as project partners, all the different actors of the I&M value chain. This is fundamental to be able to successfully execute the joint PILOTING exploitation plan. However, PILOTING partners will contribute in different ways to this PILOTING exploitation plan developing various activities.

Then, it is important to describe how each of the partners can contribute to the previously described PILOTING exploitation plan, as part of each individual exploitation plan.

PILOTING consortium has identified the following main roles and activities in the execution of the exploitation plan:

Role	Project Partners	Main activities in the execution of PILOTING exploitation plan
University/technology centre	CATEC, ETHZ, ICCS, SINTEF and USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define limits of the technology to be exploited

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support in defining main characteristics of future product or services • Support in identifying barriers • Collaboration in the industrialization plan
Robotics or system developer	ROBOTNIK, GEIR, HONEYWELL, QUASSET and INLECOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define main characteristics of product • Support in developing value propositions • Development and selection of business cases related to product commercialization • Development of the industrialization plan related to product-based business cases
Service provider	APPLUS RVIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support in understanding real end-user needs • Development of value propositions • Development and selection of business cases related to service provision • Development of the industrialization plan related to service-based business cases
End-users	CHEVRON, FERROVIAL, EGNATIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying barriers and requirements • Establishing user gains and pains • Validation and selection of most promising value propositions • Support in the development of business cases • Support in the development of the industrialization plan

Table 26. Main roles and activities in the execution of the exploitation plan.

6.2 Exploitation plan per scenario

Although the PILOTING Exploitation Plan will explore value propositions and business cases for all three scenarios, it is true that during the process there is a risk in focusing mainly on specific aspects, losing the opportunity to cover more added value propositions that combine different services and technologies together.

For this reason, it is important the role of the end-users that have a complete understanding of all the aspects related to a specific scenario (refineries, viaducts and tunnels). Then, the three PILOTING end-users (Chevron, Ferrovial and Egnatia) will also include a specific exploitation plan-related actions per scenario in order to identify added value combined propositions, not only considering technologies developed in PILOTING but also figuring out possible combinations, including other existing products or services, to come up with high impact value propositions that can lead to disruptive business cases. Moreover, PILOTING end-users will also study how the identified value propositions can be integrated into their inspection procedures in order to facilitate the future exploitation of these technologies.

Then, the following actions have been identified in the execution of the PILOTING exploitation plan related to specific aspects of the different scenarios:

- Identify the KERs that can be applied to each of the different scenarios. This task will be repeated every time the KER list is updated.
- Analyse different options combining identified value propositions.
- Study the creation of new value propositions combining new PILOTING technologies with already existing products or services.
- Assess the impact of integrating the selected value propositions in each of the scenario inspection procedures.

Next, and as a first action of the specific exploitation plan per scenario, it is described how the different end-user partners (Chevron for refineries, Ferrovial for viaducts and Egnatia for tunnels) initially identify which PILOTING KERs can be exploited in each of the scenarios.

6.2.1 Refinery scenario

Chevron considers that the following KER could be the base of future exploited technologies in the refinery use case:

KER N°	Key Exploitable result	Brief description	Exploited by
KER 1	Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots	This KER will be based on an aerial robot that is able to perform ultrasound contact inspections and obtain wall thickness measurements. Moreover, this aerial robot implements an “inspection” navigation mode where the operator can directly move the inspection sensor while the aerial robot will automatically follow it and maintain the contact with the surface.	CATEC
KER 2	GNSS-free aerial robot navigation in large areas	This KER is about an aerial robot that is able to navigate without the need of GNSS as the primary navigation system in large areas (for example a viaduct or	CATEC

		bridge). The aerial robot will be also able to follow pre-defined missions and automatically follow the corresponding flight plans.	
KER 3	Hybrid robot for pipes inspection in refineries	This KER is based on a hybrid robot that will be able to navigate in complex spaces and land on pipes. Once it is landed, it will be able to perform a complete inspection on complex pipes segments (like elbows and Ts).	CATEC
KER 4	Generic Robot Control Station	This KER is about a generic control station that will be compatible with a large number of robotics systems for I&M. The generic robot control station will be used for planning and supervision of the robotic system and it will facilitate the training of a single operator for different robotics systems.	CATEC
KER 5	Texture-based defect detection and classification	This KER is based on a software module that can segment images and classify large variety of materials and defects. The module consists of a segmentation algorithm and a trained neural network. Using an overview image and only a small number of close-up images, this AI-based solution can provide deep analysis of the whole photographed area.	HONEYWELL
KER 6	Quickly building 3D asset models	This KER is based on AssetBuilder, a webbased tool to create 3D models of assets with detailed CAD experience or tools. For robotic navigation and data presentation, 3D models are often required, but not available. Quasset is developing AssetBuilder to allow users to create 3D asset models, using parametrized parts, e.g. for manway, shell, heads, nozzles etc. AssetBuilder will support multiple asset types.	QUASSET
KER 7	Inspection data overlay on 3D assets	This KER will be based on robotic inspection data presentation module. This module offers an easily interpretable way of presenting robotic inspection data on 3D models of assets. This module supports different inspection data types and various 3D file formats. It is web-based.	QUASSET
KER 8	Asset annotation of key inspection data	This KER will be based on Asset annotation module called Asset Annotator	QUASSET

		which offers a clean and easy method to make annotations on 3D asset models quickly and easily.	
KER 10	Data Management System	This KER will be based on a set of data storage, distribution and harmonization services and solutions that will comprise the PILOTING Data Management System and Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer. The integrated solution will be able to collect heterogeneous data (incl. Inspection images and videos, on-robot sensor readings, detailed inspection task definition) from a Robot Control Station and from Sensor Systems (incl. Legacy Systems of the Infrastructure and IoT Sensors), harmonize them using specified data-models and store them using a distributed storage solution with time and location indexing capabilities. Additionally, the system will be able to provide services in order for a visualization portal to be able to retrieve data and also to define a Mission definition that will be forwarded to a Robot Control Station in order to be specialized to specific tasks. Finally, the System will be able to interact with external services (e.g. AI-based image analysis tools) by providing data retrieval and metadata (image analysis results) management services.	ICCS
KER 11	Mission Planning Interface	Exclusively humans using joystick controls currently control the GEIR crawler robots. Missions are planned mostly on paper and executed manually. A key element for standardized inspections using robots is standardizing on the mission planning and execution. Within the PILOTING project, a standardized interface for submitting a mission plan to a GEIR crawler will be developed. This interface will enable the GEIR robots to accept mission plans from different end-users by providing them with a standard input format. The economic impact from this KER will be based on the fact that asset-owners can standardize on inspection	GEIR

			plans in digital format and execute them using GEIR robots.	
KER 12	Mission Execution by Waypoint Navigation		<p>A mission for inspection using surface adhering crawlers consists of a sequence of waypoints. Such waypoints may be inspection locations (points of interests) or waypoints required for successful mission execution (i.e. points required for obstacle passing).</p> <p>One task within the PILOTING project is to enable the surface adhering inspection robots to move from one waypoint to another without the need of operator interaction. Given the waypoint navigation, execution of entire missions based on a sequence of waypoints becomes feasible.</p>	GEIR
KER 16	PILOTING I&M platform		<p>This Key Exploitable Result will be based on one of the core outcomes of the project, the PILOTING Inspection and Maintenance Platform (I&M platform) which comprises of the following key parts of the solution: the Robot Control Station, the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer as well as the Data Management System. The exploitation aim of the I&M platform is to be offered to end-users primarily in the transport and oil and gas industries and others to perform overall maintenance tasks of infrastructures during their whole lifetime, preventing accidents and fulfilling the required regulations and industrial standards. The PILOTING I&M platform will be designed following a scalable and open architecture in order to facilitate the integration of different types of robotic systems into new business cases related to inspection and maintenance.</p>	INLECOM
KER 17	Data Distribution and Harmonization component		<p>This Key Exploitable Result will be based on the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization component, which will be developed as a part of I&M platform by INLECOM. This is a vector-specific data ingestion component for IoT systems. It is related to the connectivity between I&M platform parts (including Robot Control Station, IoT Sensors and Data</p>	INLECOM

		Management System), to the data transformation to robotics-related data models as well as to the data distribution through Middleware interfaces.	
KER 19	Refinery inspection and maintenance robot	This robot will be based on an existing vehicle from Robotnik which consists on a mobile manipulator specially designed for intervention, reconnaissance and inspection missions, able to mount specific sensors and with a high mobility kinematic configuration that allows accessing adverse and rough terrains and stair climbing.	RBNK
KER 21	Localization and Mapping System in Refineries	This KER is the specialization of a localization and mapping system towards the challenging refinery scenario. The developed system will be able to map and localize by being teleoperated on a first mission or on autonomous navigation mode one a prior map is available. The main characteristics of this system is its robustness to the challenging perception posed by the infrastructure and the environment, and it high accuracy.	ETHZ

Table 27. KER to be exploited in the refinery scenario.

6.2.2 Viaduct scenario

Ferrovial considers that the following KER can be exploited in the viaduct use case:

KER N°	Key Exploitable result	Brief description	Exploited by
KER 2	GNSS-free aerial robot navigation in large areas	This KER is about an aerial robot that is able to navigate without the need of GNSS as the primary navigation system in large areas (for example a viaduct or bridge). The aerial robot will be also able to follow pre-defined missions and automatically follow the corresponding flight plans.	CATEC
KER 4	Generic Robot Control Station	This KER is about a generic control station that will be compatible with a large number of robotics systems for I&M. The generic robot control station will be used for planning and supervision of the robotic system and	CATEC

		it will facilitate the training of a single operator for different robotics systems.	
KER 5	Texture-based defect detection and classification	This KER is based on a software module that can segment images and classify large variety of materials and defects. The module consists of a segmentation algorithm and a trained neural network. Using an overview image and only a small number of close-up images, this AI-based solution can provide deep analysis of the whole photographed area.	HONEYWELL
KER 6	Quickly building 3D asset models	This KER is based on AssetBuilder, a webbased tool to create 3D models of assets with detailed CAD experience or tools. For robotic navigation and data presentation, 3D models are often required, but not available. Quasset is developing AssetBuilder to allow users to create 3D asset models, using parametrized parts, e.g. for manway, shell, heads, nozzles etc. AssetBuilder will support multiple asset types.	QUASSET
KER 7	Inspection data overlay on 3D assets	This KER will be based on robotic inspection data presentation module. This module offers an easily interpretable way of presenting robotic inspection data on 3D models of assets. This module supports different inspection data types and various 3D file formats. It is web-based.	QUASSET
KER 8	Asset annotation of key inspection data	This KER will be based on Asset annotation module called Asset Annotator which offers a clean and easy method to make annotations on 3D asset models quickly and easily.	QUASSET
KER 9	AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks	This KER will be based on a set of AI-based applications that ICCS will develop that will be able to discriminate between Inspection Images that represent healthy samples of infrastructure points with those that represent defects as well as to classify the type of defect observed. The	ICCS

		former will be based on novel detection algorithms that will be able to assist the manual annotation process of inspection data, while the latter will be based on advanced deep learning methods that will allow the automatic annotation of inspection images regarding the types of defects.	
KER 10	Data Management System	This KER will be based on a set of data storage, distribution and harmonization services and solutions that will comprise the PILOTING Data Management System and Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer. The integrated solution will be able to collect heterogeneous data (incl. Inspection images and videos, on-robot sensor readings, detailed inspection task definition) from a Robot Control Station and from Sensor Systems (incl. Legacy Systems of the Infrastructure and IoT Sensors), harmonize them using specified data-models and store them using a distributed storage solution with time and location indexing capabilities. Additionally, the system will be able to provide services in order for a visualization portal to be able to retrieve data and also to define a Mission definition that will be forwarded to a Robot Control Station in order to be specialized to specific tasks. Finally, the System will be able to interact with external services (e.g. AI-based image analysis tools) by providing data retrieval and metadata (image analysis results) management services.	ICCS
KER 13	Installation of surveying targets by aerial robots	This KER consists of an aerial robot that is able to install surveying targets on bridges or viaducts. These targets are small devices that can be used later to improve the accuracy of visual inspections (i.e. having a ruler) or to take geometric measurements of the structure with a total station (i.e. with a reflective part). This is achieved by	USE

		being in contact with the viaduct's structure. The aerial robot can perform this installation autonomously or in assisted mode.	
KER 15	Stable contact and crawling by aerial robots	This KER consists of an aerial robot that is able to stick itself to an upper horizontal surface (e.g. a viaduct's deck) and move through the surface without losing contact. This ability allows the aerial robot to reach inaccessible places (e.g. close to the bearings of a viaduct) and to gain stability to take more accurate measurements or images. In addition, an external total station can take very accurate measurements of the deflection of a bridge or viaduct.	USE
KER 16	PILOTING I&M platform	This Key Exploitable Result will be based on one of the core outcomes of the project, the PILOTING Inspection and Maintenance Platform (I&M platform) which comprises of the following key parts of the solution: the Robot Control Station, the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer as well as the Data Management System. The exploitation aim of the I&M platform is to be offered to end-users primarily in the transport and oil and gas industries and others to perform overall maintenance tasks of infrastructures during their whole lifetime, preventing accidents and fulfilling the required regulations and industrial standards. The PILOTING I&M platform will be designed following a scalable and open architecture in order to facilitate the integration of different types of robotic systems into new business cases related to inspection and maintenance.	INLECOM
KER 17	Data Distribution and Harmonization component	This Key Exploitable Result will be based on the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization component, which will be developed as a part of I&M platform by INLECOM. This is a vector-specific data ingestion	INLECOM

		component for IoT systems. It is related to the connectivity between I&M platform parts (including Robot Control Station, IoT Sensors and Data Management System), to the data transformation to robotics-related data models as well as to the data distribution through Middleware interfaces.	
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Table 28. KER to be exploited in the viaduct scenario.

6.2.3 Tunnel scenario

EGNATIA considers that the following KER could be the base of future exploited technologies in the tunnel use case:

KER N°	Key Exploitable result	Brief description	Exploited by
KER 4	Generic Robot Control Station	This KER is about a generic control station that will be compatible with a large number of robotics systems for I&M. The generic robot control station will be used for planning and supervision of the robotic system and it will facilitate the training of a single operator for different robotics systems.	CATEC
KER 5	Texture-based defect detection and classification	This KER is based on a software module that can segment images and classify a large variety of materials and defects. The module consists of a segmentation algorithm and a trained neural network. Using an overview image and only a small number of close-up images, this AI-based solution can provide deep analysis of the whole photographed area.	HONEYWELL
KER 6	Quickly building 3D asset models	This KER is based on AssetBuilder, a webbased tool to create 3D models of assets with detailed CAD experience or tools. For robotic navigation and data presentation, 3D models are often required, but not available. Quasset is developing AssetBuilder to allow users to create 3D asset models, using parametrized parts, e.g. for manway, shell, heads, nozzles etc. AssetBuilder will support multiple asset types.	QUASSET

KER 7	Inspection data overlay on 3D assets	This KER will be based on robotic inspection data presentation module. This module offers an easily interpretable way of presenting robotic inspection data on 3D models of assets. This module supports different inspection data types and various 3D file formats. It is web-based.	QUASSET
KER 8	Asset annotation of key inspection data	This KER will be based on Asset annotation module called Asset Annotator which offers a clean and easy method to make annotations on 3D asset models quickly and easily.	QUASSET
KER 9	AI-based algorithms for inspection tasks	This KER will be based on a set of AI-based applications that ICCS will develop that will be able to discriminate between Inspection Images that represent healthy samples of infrastructure points with those that represent defects as well as to classify the type of defect observed. The former will be based on novel detection algorithms that will be able to assist the manual annotation process of inspection data, while the latter will be based on advanced deep learning methods that will allow the automatic annotation of inspection images regarding the types of defects.	ICCS
KER 10	Data Management System	This KER will be based on a set of data storage, distribution and harmonization services and solutions that will comprise the PILOTING Data Management System and Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer. The integrated solution will be able to collect heterogeneous data (incl. Inspection images and videos, on-robot sensor readings, detailed inspection task definition) from a Robot Control Station and from Sensor Systems (incl. Legacy Systems of the Infrastructure and IoT Sensors), harmonize them using specified data-models and store them using a	ICCS

			distributed storage solution with time and location indexing capabilities. Additionally, the system will be able to provide services in order for a visualization portal to be able to retrieve data and also to define a Mission definition that will be forwarded to a Robot Control Station in order to be specialized to specific tasks. Finally, the System will be able to interact with external services (e.g. AI-based image analysis tools) by providing data retrieval and metadata (image analysis results) management services.	
KER 14	Tunnel close visual inspection by aerial robots		This KER consists of an aerial robot that is able to perform visual inspections inside of a tunnel. This implies solving the aerodynamic and localization problems in such a narrow and constrained environment as a tunnel. It will be achieved through robust control techniques and SLAM algorithms. In addition, this robot could be equipped with a lighting system to be able to take close images of the infrastructure with enough quality.	USE
KER 16	PILOTING platform	I&M	This Key Exploitable Result will be based on one of the core outcomes of the project, the PILOTING Inspection and Maintenance Platform (I&M platform) which comprises of the following key parts of the solution: the Robot Control Station, the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer as well as the Data Management System. The exploitation aim of the I&M platform is to be offered to end-users primarily in the transport and oil and gas industries and others to perform overall maintenance tasks of infrastructures during their whole lifetime, preventing accidents and fulfilling the required regulations and industrial standards. The PILOTING I&M platform will be designed following a scalable and open	INLECOM

		architecture in order to facilitate the integration of different types of robotic systems into new business cases related to inspection and maintenance.	
KER 17	Data Distribution and Harmonization component	This Key Exploitable Result will be based on the I&M Data Distribution and Harmonization component, which will be developed as a part of I&M platform by INLECOM. This is a vector-specific data ingestion component for IoT systems. It is related to the connectivity between I&M platform parts (including Robot Control Station, IoT Sensors and Data Management System), to the data transformation to robotics-related data models as well as to the data distribution through Middleware interfaces.	INLECOM
KER 18	Overall tunnel inspection robot	This robot will be based on the automation of an electric cart, performed on a 4 wheeled vehicle which will be prepared for autonomous operations. Its carrying capacity will be increased; including the installation of an elevation crane to position the sensor loads (several types of cameras and LIDARs) up to 3 meter high. This robot will also incorporate a special platform for aerial robot take-off and landing. Special effort will be put for developing protocols and including the hardware that will provide a safe operation of the solution.	RBNK
KER 20	Mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception	This KER will allow a mobile platform navigate to inspection points autonomously using onboard perception to detect and avoid any unexpected obstacles. Navigation is based on a simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) system that has been specialized for areas with very sparse visual and structural features.	SINTEF

Table 29. KER to be exploited in the tunnel scenario.

6.3 Initial identification of joint exploitation plans

The following KERs have been identified as potential technologies that could be used as a baseline to develop joint exploitation plans:

- Autonomous navigation in tunnels using onboard sensor module (SINTEF and ROBOTNIK)
- Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots (CATEC, University of Seville and APPLUS)
- PILOTING I&M platform (ICCS, INLECOM, CATEC and APPLUS)
- Mission planning interface (QUASSET and WTR)
- Localization and Mapping System in Refineries for Ground Robots (ETHZ and ROBOTNIK)
- End-to-end solution for pipe UT (Ultrasonic Testing) inspections (QUASSET, CATEC and WTR)

In order to explain in more detail these identified potential exploitation opportunities, value propositions have been developed using the value propositions canvas template (see Section 5.3). The six value propositions are shown next:

Value proposition 1: Autonomous navigation in tunnels using onboard sensor module (SINTEF and ROBOTNIK)

CUSTOMER PROFILE	
Customer jobs	Pains
Localize inspection points of interest in a tunnel.	Find the position with sufficient accuracy in a GNSS denied environment with limited structural features. Installation and maintenance of additional markers or other equipment for localization in tunnels. Cost and effort for use of total station for localization.
Gains	
Localize and return to points of interest with high accuracy with less effort, eventually allowing for autonomous inspection vehicles.	

VALUE PROPOSITION	
Pain relievers	Gain creators
Positioning without the need of external systems such as GNSS or total station by using sensors on the vehicle instead.	All necessary sensors and compute units are located on the vehicle, such that the operation can be made autonomous. Reduced costs since access to measurement location does not require any additional infrastructure or equipment
Products and services	
Sensor pack for localization that can be integrated with a vehicle, both for vehicles with different level of autonomy and for manually controlled vehicles. Inspection vehicle with accurate localization functionality for tunnels.	

Value proposition 2: Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots (CATEC, University of Seville and APPLUS)

CUSTOMER PROFILE	
Customer jobs	Pains
<p>Perform wall thickness inspections periodically to large tanks following the required regulations or standards</p> <p>Submit or save in custody an inspection report following the required standards or regulations</p>	<p>Costly and long inspection due to difficult access locations (at certain height)</p> <p>If work at height methods are used (scaffolding or rope access), then also safety concerns arise</p> <p>Most of the time and cost just to access to a location, and not to perform the inspection itself</p>
Gains	
<p>Perform the complete inspection of a tank, fulfilling all the requirements of the required regulations or standards and in less time and with less cost than with other alternative methods (magnetic robots, rope access, scaffolding, etc.)</p>	

VALUE PROPOSITION	
Pain relievers	Gain creators
<p>Much less safety risk for the inspectors or other personnel</p> <p>No need to organize or synchronize with other companies for the deployment of complementary infrastructure. All the necessary equipment is provided by the same company (unlike with work at height when some time the scaffolding part is deployed by one company and the inspection by another one)</p>	<p>Reduce time to perform the inspection</p> <p>Reduce costs since access to measurement location does not require any additional infrastructure or equipment</p>
Products and services	
<p>Wall thickness inspection service with aerial robots of large Oil&Gas infrastructures, such as tanks, including the elaboration of the required inspection report</p>	

Value proposition 3: PILOTING I&M platform (ICCS, INLECOM, CATEC and APPLUS)

CUSTOMER PROFILE	
Customer jobs	Pains
<p>Refinery inspectors: Manual inspections missions are kept in the records system, the Asset Integrity database (AId), based on which inspection plans and calendar intervals are created.</p> <p>Viaduct inspection: After the implementation of on-site inspections, the collected material along with the corresponding information of the infrastructure's health state has to be downloaded and transformed into a digital, readable and organised format, formulating a report that is submitted to the infrastructure manager.</p> <p>Tunnel inspection: Recorded damages have to be categorised by inspectors in reports, including the evaluation of collected data and defect grading. The inspection results need to be integrated into the FHMA-1 scale condition rating system.</p>	<p>Costly and time-consuming process for the engineering firms to collect all the inspected information (e.g. images, notes, reports, etc.) and to transform it into valuable digitalised knowledge.</p> <p>Absence of an automated process and extra effort to collect and organise the inspection data from the robotic systems</p> <p>Prone on information inconsistency resulting from inspector's subjective judgement.</p> <p>Sometimes cumbersome and inconsistent reporting of inspection (and maintenance) results.</p>
Gains	
<p>Reduce the time and cost required for the collection, transformation and storing of different data from various sources following the standardised protocols. Autonomously monitor the inspection process, to support maintenance planning, inspection efficiency and ultimately the health status of road infrastructures and safer working conditions for workers.</p>	

VALUE PROPOSITION	
Pain relievers	Gain creators
<p>Results of the autonomously and remote inspection missions will be easily handled, elaborating and presented under a scalable digitalised form that will enable the inspectors to correlate different data sources allowing them to detect and monitor any defects.</p> <p>Detailed 3D representation of structural sites could be retrieved at any time in the case, which allows the better association of the collected data to the inspection location, or subsequently, apply any modifications and revisions are required.</p> <p>Perform inspection missions under an automated and safe environment allowing the remote navigation of various sensors. Collected observations will be accompanied by time and location indexing functionalities allowing the localisation and detection of any issues/faults.</p>	<p>Giving inspectors an improved, more accurate and safe visual understanding of the infrastructure's health, allowing the detailed and dedicated inspection plans following the results of previous local inspection missions.</p> <p>Automated generation of reports and data collections following the international and local standards.</p> <p>Reduce time and the cost of data transformation and storing allowing to further expand the monitoring systems that are used.</p> <p>Data can be collected and organized for any industry scenario (refineries, viaducts and tunnels) using the same platform.</p>
Products and services	
<p>A scalable standardised I&M Platform (RCS, DDHL & DMS) will allow the pilot-end users as well as any engineering inspection company to perform complete inspection tasks of infrastructures autonomously, and make accessible the different information data following under scalable, standardised and harmonised services.</p>	

Value proposition 4: Mission planning interface (QUASSET and WTR)

CUSTOMER PROFILE	
Customer jobs	Pains
<p>Each inspection requires a degree of mission preparation that happens before going to the asset. This activity may encompass the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determine the work scope form asset owner requirements - Gathering of required asset data and results of previous inspections - Process asset data for use in inspection - Selection of inspection methods and tools - Creation, selection and preparation of inspection report - Effort estimation and quotation 	<p>Today these activities are mostly carried out on paper as preparation before the mission.</p> <p>During the mission, only paper or pdf documents guide the inspector in carrying out the mission plan.</p> <p>Relevant data comes in a variety of formats and storage locations.</p> <p>No direct link between mission preparation, execution, and subsequent reporting.</p> <p>A significant amount of mission planning remains to be completed when on site.</p> <p>Report generation after mission is completed from various data fragments such as paper notes, saved images and drawings.</p>
Gains	
<p>Inspection provider able to specify mission plan prior to onsite deployment.</p> <p>Reporting consistency with desired scope and agreed mission plan.</p> <p>Trust in quality of mission execution.</p> <p>Lower cost or duration from reduced effort in planning and reporting.</p>	

VALUE PROPOSITION	
Pain relievers	Gain creators
<p>Central digital repository of relevant mission data.</p> <p>Export of mission plan to inspection tool to guide inspector through mission or autonomous execution by the tool.</p> <p>Closing the data gap between results of previous inspections, data gathering and reporting.</p> <p>Minimizing planning on-site to reduce downtime.</p> <p>Less paper handling when on-site for instructions and manually filling out report.</p> <p>Increased consistency between planned and executed work.</p>	<p>Streamline mission planning phase.</p> <p>Minimize inspection duration and resulting asset downtime by reducing remaining mission planning work onsite.</p>
Products and services	
<p>Mission planning software that utilizes available asset and inspection data and creates a mission plan both for the inspection tool and inspector.</p>	

Value proposition 5: Localization and Mapping System in Refineries for Ground Robots (ETHZ and ROBOTNIK)

CUSTOMER PROFILE	
Customer jobs	Pains
<p>Performing frequent, routine inspections</p> <p>Collecting comparable measurements over extended time periods</p> <p>Enabling other jobs that require localization w.r.t. a map (e.g. valve regulation or autonomous taxiing between teleoperated inspection sites).</p>	<p>When performing repetitive tasks, humans can get distracted, forget steps and make mistakes.</p> <p>Humans labor is expensive, especially at night or at remote locations.</p> <p>Humans have trouble maintaining measurement consistency over extended time periods or when staff members rotate.</p> <p>Humans could be hurt due to accidents or repeated exposure to harmful substances.</p> <p>Logging the location of discovered defects and finding them again for subsequent assessments or repairs can require significant effort from both the inspectors and service providers.</p>
Gains	
<p>Accurate, precise inspection over extended time periods without requiring human intervention or the installation and maintenance of localization infrastructure.</p>	

VALUE PROPOSITION	
Pain relievers	Gain creators
<p>Machine memory and attention</p> <p>Anytime inspection</p> <p>Robotic precision and accuracy</p> <p>Less risk to human inspectors</p> <p>Automatic, metric localization</p>	<p>Autonomous robots will repeatedly and consistently perform the exact steps that are prescribed by their mission plan.</p> <p>Autonomous inspection data collection reduces human personnel costs while improving test coverage.</p> <p>Accurate localization allows robots to collect precise and accurate measurements over extended time periods, without ever forgetting an inspection step.</p> <p>Performing tasks in dangerous environments with robots can reduce risk to humans, while increasing efficiency by reducing the need to shut down dangerous equipment or temporarily clear harmful substances.</p> <p>Defect reports can automatically be annotated with their metric location in the map, facilitating contextual understanding of the reports offsite and making the defects easier to find by onsite staff.</p>
Products and services	
<p>A robust and accurate localization and mapping system to be used in teleoperated, semi-autonomous, and autonomous navigation modes to carry out inspection in a refinery.</p>	

Value proposition 6: End-to-end solution for pipe UT (Ultrasonic Testing) inspections (QUASSET, CATEC and WTR)

CUSTOMER PROFILE	
Customer jobs	Pains
<p>Plan and perform periodic inspections of pipe wall thicknesses using UT methods and following best practices on inspection procedures and safety regulations.</p> <p>Analyse inspection results and provide an inspection report to the asset owners, including findings and recommendations in line with industry standards.</p>	<p>Workflow: Inspection planning is traditionally done using documents, manually distributed via email and requires manual executions, which can be suboptimal for enforcing modern best practices and potentially erroneous.</p> <p>Cost and time: Accessing pipes located at height demands a lot of costly and time-consuming preparation of the inspection site (e.g.: building scaffolding, mounting ladders or mechanical lifts, etc.).</p> <p>Safety: Inspection tasks often expose workers to dangerous working conditions such as working at height or near hazardous areas.</p> <p>Data integrity: The stressing working conditions combined with the human factors can impact the reliability of asset integrity assessments, which can lead to catastrophic failures.</p>
Gains	
<p>Optimized workflow to perform complete inspection workflow of pipe wall thicknesses inspections with innovative digital and robotic solutions, reducing costs and time, increasing safety, and offering better asset integrity assessments.</p>	

VALUE PROPOSITION	
Pain relievers	Gain creators
<p>Modern inspection planning leveraging asset 3D models and interactive annotations to visualize and share inspection locations and inspection tasks.</p> <p>HYBRID robotic platform combining an autonomous aerial robot to reach pipes at height and a satellite robot equipped with UT probes to perform the measurement.</p> <p>The use of robots allows inspectors to work remotely from dangerous inspection locations and thus minimizing unnecessary safety risks.</p> <p>Interactive visualization of the UT scan data and mission playback in context of asset 3D models, to ensure the quality of the interpretation of inspection data and make well-informed decisions.</p>	<p>Digital workflow to enable an optimized inspection planning and ensure that inspection requirements and procedures are fulfilled.</p> <p>Robotic solutions designed for fast deployment and minimizing required preparation at the inspection site, thus reducing costs and time.</p> <p>Increased work safety by using robots instead of human workers to navigate at hazardous inspection locations.</p> <p>Better asset integrity assessment thanks to more reliable data, improved data visualization and comprehensive inspection reports.</p>
Products and services	
<p>End-to-end Pipe wall thickness inspection solution based on 3D technology and advanced robotic platform, covering all aspects of inspections from intelligent inspection planning to the elaboration of standardized inspection reports. Inspection Service Providers can use the solution to offer improved and more competitive Pipe UT Inspection services.</p>	

6.4 Industrialization roadmap

Although the industrialization plan will not be developed until the end of the project, it is important to have in mind industrialization-related aspects from the beginning of the design and development activities. Especially important is to understand the possible requirements that will be completely indispensable in a future industrialization of the technology. Although in PILOTING, the developed technologies will not be qualified or certified, it is necessary that these new technologies will be designed in such a way that a future qualification or certification does not imposed a complete redesign of the system, or even worse, will prevent its industrialization.

Then, the following activities will be required before the industrialization plan is developed:

1. **Identify end-users requirements related to its future industrialization (M1-M6).** In particular requirements related with obtaining permits to operate robotic systems in their infrastructure.
2. **Assess legal, ethical and societal aspects for each of the selected value propositions (M7-M36),** and then, check that the current designs and systems fulfil them. If there is any aspect that is not fulfilled, modify the value proposition until its fulfil all legal, ethical and societal identified aspects.

3. **Assess the technological level for each of the subsystems required to exploit the business case (M37-M46)** taking into consideration the demonstrations and end-users evaluation to be developed in WP8 activities.
4. **Estimate the costs and time for industrializing the system fulfilling the needed standards and regulations that apply to the specific business case (M46-M48).**

On the other hand, PILOTING has also as an objective the long term sustainability of the PILOTING I&M platform. Then, the following steps are considered to work towards this objective:

- Organization of the previously commented innovation workshop in M32 with brainstorming sessions for connecting technology and service providers with potential end-users both within and outside the project consortium (e.g., PILOTING end-user group).
- Market analysis and identification of potential stakeholders.
- Market positioning of the envisioned service, identification of added value and the product differentiator.
- Identification of potential business models (e.g., Platform as a Service).
- Identification of market segments, potential investors/sponsors/VCs and further funding possibilities.
- Ownership and shares identification.
- Investigation of a spin-off initiative organized between the foreground owners.

6.5 Overall exploitation and industrialization timeline

The following Gantt illustrates the timeline of the different tasks and activities to be developed within PILOTING project in relation with the presented exploitation and industrialization plans, and also the activities related with the long-term sustainability of the PILOTING I&M platform.

As it can be observed from the Gantt (see Figure 4), all the tasks and activities are consistent with the global timeframe of the different plans.

7. Monitoring of the exploitation activities

The exploitation activities will be regularly evaluated and monitored during the project lifetime through a series of KPIs defined by the PILOTING consortium. Table 30 shows the KPIs defined in the project proposals related to the future exploitation of PILOTING technologies.

<i>Exploitation KPI</i>	<i>Performance indicator</i>	<i>Target value</i>
Value propositions	Number of value propositions initially developed	At least 6
Business model	Number of complete business models	At least 3
Industrialization plan	Number of industrialization plans for the developed business models	At least 1
PILOTING workshops	Organization of workshops with feedback about exploitation aspects from external stakeholders	3
Interaction from external stakeholders	Interaction with external stakeholders about PILOTING exploitation aspects	50
Participation in standardization bodies	Number of standardization bodies that PILOTING partners are collaborating with	3
PILOTING I&M platform sustainability	Business plan for long term sustainability	1

Table 30. Exploitation KPIs

8. Introduction to Dissemination plan

PILOTING intends to maximize the dissemination impact of its outputs through the execution of the Dissemination Plan. Then, this plan has as objectives determining the list of dissemination and communication activities towards the potential target audiences, and also the metrics to measure the execution of these activities.

In order to fulfil these objectives, PILOTING Dissemination Plan has been defined in five steps which are carefully described in the following sections (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Dissemination plan steps.

9. Dissemination objectives

One of the most important steps for setting the dissemination strategy is to clearly define the objectives to be achieved. Overall dissemination objectives of the PILOTING project are summarized as follows:

- Create and enhance the **visibility of the project** and its most important outputs.
 - Development of a visual identity.
 - Project website development and updates.
 - Establishment and updates of PILOTING social media profiles.
 - Project presentation at different events.
- Organisation of **PILOTING User group** in order of disseminate the project's results and receive feedback from the I&M industrial community.
- Pave the way for **wide-spread acceptance and implementation of the project results**.
 - Organisation of PILOTING workshops.
 - Presentation of project's results in relevant conferences
 - Academic and technological journal articles and publications
- **Clustering with other projects and initiatives**, including RIMA DIH, under the framework of robotics, structural inspection, non-destructive testing and Oil&Gas and Civil/Transport inspection, and establish links with them in order to follow their progress and validate the potential use or integration of their results and best practices into PILOTING project.

10. Target Audience

The PILOTING project will conduct various dissemination activities to maximize the project impact, ranging from stakeholder workshop to one-to-one engagement with infrastructure managers and owners.

The identified target audience of the project will include:

End users	Oil&Gas refineries, chemical industries. Bridge/tunnels owners/managers/ operators.
Scientific/research communities	Research institutes, universities and etc.
Industry (I&M community)	SMEs and other companies able to use technical products, derived from PILOTING, during its inspections
Industry (Robotics community)	SMEs and other companies that develop robotics-based solutions
Public Institutions	Policy markers and regulatory entities
Standardization entities	Like EUROCAE, AIOTI, API, IEC, OGC, etc.
General public	All other

Figure 6. PILOTING Target Audience.

11. Dissemination objectives and channels

Once the target audience has been identified, the dissemination objectives and channels can be defined. An indicative list is depicted in the Table 31:

Target group	Dissemination objectives	Dissemination channels
End users	Raise awareness about the solutions to be derived from PILOTING project, and on their impact on safety, daily work, operational conditions, safety business continuity, and savings in inspection, assessment and maintenance costs.	European end-user symposiums, professional magazines (paper and web), specialized websites/web-portals, and talks organised for specialised audiences
Scientific/ research communities	Update this community about scientific results of PILOTING project.	Posters and talks at international conferences, workshops and exhibitions; Peer-reviewed journal publications (see Table 33 and Table 34).
Industry	Promote the results obtained in the framework of the project. Find candidates who will support the technology transfer, and then the exploitation, of PILOTING technologies/products/services.	Through Digital Innovation Hubs (like RIMA), clusters and professional fair shows, and talks organised for specialised audiences. Three workshops with PILOTING User group members are planned in M6, M32 y M48.
Public Institutions	Raise awareness about the safety, legal, societal and economic benefits brought by the PILOTING solution.	EC institutions (EASA, GSA, etc.) and communications to National institutions.
Standardization entities	Communication of best practices and lessons learnt	Standardization entities like EUROCAE, AIOTI, API, IEC, OGC, etc.
General public	Increase public awareness of the project's objectives and activities. Information to the public will emphasize indirect benefits obtained when improving inspection of infrastructures like decreasing in work accidents, traffic jams due to non-availability of transport infrastructures and pollution due to accidents in refineries.	Press releases, project website, workshops and social media (Linkedin and Twitter).

Table 31. Dissemination objectives and channels

12. Communication and dissemination tools

12.1 Communication Tools

Communication activities aimed at promoting the project and its impact to larger audiences, including groups beyond the project own community, and raising awareness on sensitive issues, such as, the safety of the inspectors in difficult to access areas. In regards to the public at large they are essential to ensure i) a coordinated image for enhancing project visibility; ii) translate the scientific results into public outreach for the general public.

12.1.1 Visual identity

With the objective to give a coherent identity to all publications and presentations related to the project, a visual identity has been developed. The visual identity includes the project logo (see Figure 7), flyer (see Annex I: Flyer layout), roll-up (see Annex II: Roll-up layout), poster (see Annex III: Poster layout) and templates (to documents and presentations) which must be used by partners when presenting their work.

Figure 7. PILOTING logo.

All this material is available in the project's repository, Basecamp, in the folder Docs & Files → Public Material.

12.1.2 Project website

The project website (www.piloting-project.eu) is one of the most important communication channels of PILOTING and it will serve as a key element of engagement with the identified target groups. The website aims to provide all basic information about the project as well as up-to-date information in relation to the project activities to stakeholders and general public such as public deliverables, publications, newsletter, news, events, etc.

In addition, the website provides a contact point for the different target groups of PILOTING project, the email address: piloting-project@catec.aero.

For more information about the project website see D10.1- Project Website. This deliverable is available internally to the consortium at the project's repository, Basecamp, in the folder Docs & Files → WP10 Exploitation, communication and dissemination → D10.1 Project Website. In addition, it has been publicly shared in the PILOTING community through the Zenodo open access

repository: zenodo.org/communities/piloting/, which is also available in the project website, under Publication and datasets subsection.

12.1.3 Social media

PILOTING will be promoted through different social media channels, which have been created to maximize the impact and give visibility to project event and news.

The project has established the PILOTING LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/h2020-piloting-project/>) and the PILOTING Twitter account (https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU) where all PILOTING project progress and results will be uploaded.

These social media accounts will be daily managed by the project coordinator, CATEC. However, all partners will participate by providing news, posting and retweeting regularly, so this is actually a collaborative effort among all partners.

In addition, each partner will use its own social media accounts to disseminate the main result of the project.

The videos produced during the development of the project will be uploaded in the partners YouTube channels and will also be available in the multimedia section of the PILOTING website.

➤ **LinkedIn Profile**

LinkedIn is a networking platform designed for the professional community, which makes it the perfect tool to establish connections with professionals who are in the same interest and be part in group discussions.

PILOTING LinkedIn profile will enable to establish a network with most of PILOTING target audience as bride/tunnels/owners/managers/operators, research institutes, individuals and entities involved in any of the fields related to PILOTING. All the project's news will be published on LinkedIn and partners will have the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes to attract stakeholders. PILOTING's LinkedIn profile will follow relevant experts to be updated with the latest news and developments.

Figure 8 provides an overview of PILOTING's LinkedIn profile.

Figure 8. PILOTING LinkedIn profile.

➤ **Twitter account**

Twitter is a flexible platform that allows posting news, status updates, links to multimedia content and more in real time. This platform will increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audience.

Figure 9 provides an overview of PILOTING’s Twitter account.

Figure 9. PILOTING's Twitter account

12.1.4 Radio/TV interviews

This type of tools will be used to make a wide European audience aware of the PILOTING concepts and what the potential benefits for the economy, environment, society, associated with the application of the project results can actually be.

Radio/TV interviews will be promoted, as much as possible through the whole project, in order to disseminate PILOTING project to a wider audience.

12.1.5 Periodic press-releases

Periodic press releases will present specific PILOTING's achievements that can be interesting to the industrial companies, SEMs and general public, as the project launch, the field tests and the project's dissemination events.

Project's press releases will be developed by the all the consortium to national and/or international, electronic and printed media. In order to coordinate press releases and increase their impact, a press release coordinator has been appointed per country (see Table 32).

Spain	FERROVIAL
Greece	ICCS
Switzerland	GEIR
France	CHEVRON
Czech Republic	HONWEYWELL
Netherlands	APPLUS RVIS
Norway	SINTEF

Table 32. Press release coordinator per country

Moreover, each PILOTING press release coordinator will use their communication department contacts to communicate the progress of the project and will be responsible for translations to national languages.

On the other hand, project partners can also publish national press releases at any time in order to maximize the dissemination of PILOTING project.

The project consortium will produce at least one press release per year and per participating country at this will be disseminated at national level.

12.1.6 Electronic newsletters

An electronic newsletter will be produced and issued periodically every six months providing updates and relevant information. Each newsletter will be distributed to project identified stakeholders, contacts and liaised projects initiatives in order to present the project progress and upcoming events.

The first draft of the newsletter will be produced by the Innovation, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (IDEM) and this will be sent to all consortium partners for review. The partners will send their feedback and then the IDEM will send the newsletter to all partners one week before publishing for review. All the newsletters will also be uploaded to the project's repository, Basecamp, and will remain available.

As mentioned above, the project consortium will produce a newsletter every six months, that is, 2 newsletters per year. The newsletters will be disseminated through the news tap of PILOTING website, social networks of PILOTING and PILOTING User Group. The list of newsletter recipients will be constantly enriched both by all project partners and via subscription sending a mail of interest to the project's mail: piloting-project@catec.aero, available in the PILOTING website.

12.2 Dissemination tools

The dissemination activities aim to the public disclosure of the project results. In this aspect they are strongly correlated and logically coupled with communication activities. All the public deliverables, scientific publications, presentations will be uploaded on the project website that give a crosslink with the communication activities.

Dissemination tools will be implemented to reach more specific audiences relevant to PILOTING project. The most important tools are listed below. The list of dissemination tools may be updated as new opportunities emerge.

12.2.1 PILOTING User Group

In order to reach a large set of external entities and stakeholders a list of contacts, the PILOTING User Group, will be created with the valuable contribution of all partners.

The PILOTING User Group will be used to discuss and verify user needs and requirements and operational system capabilities, and also to disseminate and obtain feedback of project results from a wide group of stakeholders, maximizing the possibilities for future exploitation of the technologies.

The PILOTING User Group will remain updated and accessible to all consortium partners in the project repository, Basecamp, in the file: Docs&Files → WP10 Exploitation, communication and dissemination → PILOTING User Group → PILOTING User Group list.

In the first 6 months of the project, there are already 192 members that form the PILOTING User Group.

12.2.2 Publications

A major effort will be made towards publishing peer reviewed scientific and technical papers to well respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines and respective conference proceedings. This task will be undertaken mostly by the university and research centers partners and publications will cover several fields of the work performed within the PILOTING project.

PILOTING will fulfil the H2020 Open Access to publications mandate. Then, refereed publications will be limited to those journals, conferences and workshops that provide open access ('green' or 'gold').

Table 33 shows a list of potential journals focusing on the project areas.

<i>Area</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Journal(s)</i>
Oil&Gas Inspection	1	Reliability Engineering & System Safety
	2	Applied Energy
	3	Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering
Transport inspection and civil infrastructures	4	Automation in Construction
	5	Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology
	6	ASCE Journal of Structural Eng
Robotic systems	7	International Journal of Robotics Research
	8	Journal of Field Robotics
	9	IEEE Trans. on Robotics
	10	IEEE Trans. on Mechatronics
	11	IEEE Trans. on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence

Computer Vision, Pattern Recognition, Artificial Intelligence	12	International Journal of Computer Vision
	13	Journal of Machine Learning Research
	14	Cognitive Computation

Table 33. List with relevant journals to PILOTING.

12.2.3 Organization of workshops

One of the project's major dissemination activities is the organisation of a number of dedicated PILOTING workshops with the basic aim to disseminate the project progress and results as well as to receive feedback from stakeholders.

Three end-users workshops have been planned:

- Month 6: an end-user workshop to present, and discuss the end-user requirements, along with the functional specifications of the PILOTING I&M platform and the results of the SoEL studies. Due to the current covid-19 situation in Europe, this workshop has been organized as a webinar on June 25th (see Section 5.2).
- Month 32: an end-user workshop to present the beta release and first evaluation results. Also, an innovation session will be organized with brainstorming sessions for connecting technology and service providers with potential end-users.
- Month 48: an end-user workshop focusing on the project final outcomes, and the obtained evaluation results, especially the comparison with tradition I&M procedures. The target is to increase the understanding from the application stakeholders of the potential for deploying robotics in I&M operations.

12.2.4 PILOTING presentation at relevant events

The work performed in PILOTING will be disseminated also through presentations and posters at relevant transport, inspection, non-destructive testing as well as robotics and inspection conferences, workshops and special sessions during the project runtime.

Table 34 shows a list with the relevant conferences and events identified related to the PILOTING field.

<i>Area</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Journal(s)</i>
Oil&Gas Inspection	1	AUTOMA (Oil&Gas automation and digitalization congress)
	2	World Conference for Inspection and Maintenance Robotics
Transport inspection and civil infrastructures	4	ITA COSUF
	5	Transport Research Arena (TRA) Conference
	6	Bridge and Tunnels Inspectors Conference
	7	National Association of State Highway and Transportation Unions
	8	Bridge and Tunnel Inspection Conference
Robotic systems	9	ICRA — IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation

	10	IROS — IEEE/RSJ International Conference
	11	euRobotics / ERF
	12	CASE — IEEE Automation Science and Engineering
Computer Vision, Pattern Recognition, Artificial Intelligence	13	ICIP – IEEE International Conference on Image Processing
	14	NIPS - Neural Information Processing Systems
	15	CoRL- Conference on Robot Learning
	16	ICML -International Conference in Machine Learning

Table 34. List with relevant conferences and events to PILOTING.

A list with all the PILOTING participation and presentations at events has been uploaded in the PILOTING repository, Basecamp, in the folder Docs&Files → WP10 Exploitation, communication and dissemination → Dissemination Activities-Events. This document will be kept up to date throughout the duration of the project in order to reflect PILOTING participation in different events.

However, and due to the covid-19 situation, there is a lot of uncertainty about which specific events will be maintained or not in the next years. This is the reason why a detailed list of events to assist and present PILOTING project has not been included in this deliverable.

Also due to the covid-19 situation in Europe, a large number of events has been cancelled or postponed in the first semester of 2020. Therefore, the presentation of PILOTING project in dissemination events will be very limited during 2020. It is expected that this situation will improve during the last part of 2020 and on-going. In case, the covid-19 situation in Europe will not allow the organization of this type of events in Europe after 2020, other alternatives will be explored such as:

- Participation in virtual conferences.
- Participation in virtual events.
- Organization of virtual workshops.

12.2.5 Clustering with other projects and initiatives

Another measure to maximize the impact of PILOTING is to create synergies and further exploit the opportunities for collaboration with project which share the same field of research and exploitation and respond to similar stakeholders while working on different issues.

Clustering with other project under the framework of robotics, structural inspection, non-destructive testing and Oil&Gas and Civil/Transport inspection and establish links with them will allow to follow their progress and validate the potential use or integration of their results into the PILOTING.

The list of relevant projects identified in the PILOTING field is as follows:

- HYFLIERS: <https://www.oulu.fi/hyfliers/>
- RESIST: <http://www.resistproject.eu/>
- RIMA: <https://rimanetwork.eu/>
- ATLANTIS: <https://www.atlantis-h2020.eu/>
- METRICS: <https://metricsproject.eu/>
- AERIAL-CORE: <https://aerial-core.eu/>

Collaboration agreements and cross-dissemination actions will be promoted during PILOTING project. For example, during the first PILOTING workshop held on June 25th, there was a slot where RIMA, ATLANTIS, AERIAL-CORE, and METRICS projects were presented by their representatives.

Especially important will be the relation with RIMA (DIH network oriented to robotics for I&M) where lessons learnt and best practices can also be shared. Also, new projects and initiatives will be added to this list in case they are identified during project lifetime.

13. Monitoring of the dissemination activities

The dissemination and communication activities will be regularly evaluated and monitored during the project lifetime. PILOTING consortium has agreed to a series of KPIs detailed below.

<i>Communication / Dissemination means</i>	<i>Targeted communities</i>	<i>Performance Indicators</i>	<i>Target Value</i>	<i>Reach level</i>
<i>Logo and Poster</i>	General public	Logo and Poster designed	1 logo, 1 poster layout	International
<i>Local media presence</i>	General public	N° of appearances (TV, newspaper, radio, magazines)	One appearance per year per participating country	National
<i>Social media presence</i>	General public	N° of posts performed, social media metrics (N° of followers)	One LinkedIn and one Twitter post per week, 500 followers	International
<i>Content delivery platforms (e.g. YouTube)</i>	General public	N° of channels, performed posts	Project channel in at least one delivery platform with a minimum of 3 posts per year	International
<i>Press releases</i>	Industry, general public	N° of press releases issued	One press release per year per participating country	National and International
<i>Newsletters</i>	Industry and Public Institutions	N° of newsletters released	2 newsletters per year	International
<i>Publications</i>	Research and Industry	N° of papers published	> 10 peer-reviewed scientific journals and conference publications	International
<i>PILOTING User Group</i>	Industry	N° of participants	At least 100 members	International
<i>Clustering with other projects</i>	Research and Industry	N° of projects collaborating with	RIMA DIH and at least three more projects	International

<i>PILOTING workshops</i>	Industry and end-users	N° of workshops	At least three during the project	International
<i>Participation in relevant events</i>	End-users, standardization bodies, public institutions, industry and research	N° of events per years	Participation in at least 2 events per year	International

Table 35. Dissemination and Communication KPIs

13.1 Dissemination Procedure

A dissemination procedure has been created for the proper monitoring and recording of the project's dissemination activities.

The main objectives of the procedure are to:

- Produce high quality PILOTING publications, presentations and other dissemination material;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Monitoring and record of the communication and dissemination activities of the project in an effective and efficient way.

The PILOTING dissemination procedure has been defined with the agreement of all consortium partners.

13.1.1 Step by step procedure

For upcoming dissemination activities

At least 45 days before the performance of any dissemination activity related to PILOTING project (except for already approved public material), the initiator of the dissemination activity:

- 1) Submits the dissemination request, allowing for minimum 45 days before submission deadline, via e-mail to PILOTING Steering Committee (SC) piloting-steering@catec.aero;
- 2) Fill in the Excel file Dissemination Activities-Events the planned dissemination activity (this document can be find in [Basecamp](#));
- 3) Shares the material (abstract, publication, presentation, poster, article, press release etc) to the PILOTING repository, Basecamp, creating a folder that reflects to the event in the WP10 Exploitation, communication and dissemination folder;
- 4) The PC and SC have to reply to the dissemination request within next 30 days; If no answer is received due to the set deadline it is taken as an approval.

In case of:

Approval: the initiator of the dissemination activity may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned dissemination activity.

Conflict/objection: Project coordinator and SC can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example, in case of overlaps or risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. The objection has to include a clear reasoning as well as a precise request for necessary modifications. In case of conflict, the issue is discussed among the Project Coordinator, the SC, and the involved partners. Then, modifications and additions can be suggested. Once the required indications and modifications have been added by the initiator of the dissemination activity, the material can be proposed again to SC.

NOTE: In case of partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to PILOTING, then the information to the Project Coordinator and SC has to be sent 2 months before the realisation of this dissemination activity.

For performed dissemination activities

Within 10 working days after the realisation of the approved dissemination activity, the initiator of the dissemination activities:

- 1) Provides the IDEM with filled dissemination activity report and the presented dissemination material.
- 2) All material will be archive in the Basecamp.
- 3) It will be also highly appreciated if the organiser of every dissemination activity provides to IDEM with some photos of their participation at the different events.

13.2 Acknowledgement

All the dissemination and communication material must clearly acknowledge the European Union's contribution in all publications or in conjunction with activities for which the allocated grants are used.

In this respect, the EU emblem (see Figure 10), associated to a sentence that imply the EU contribution, is required on all their publications, posters, programmes and other products realised under the grant agreement.

Figure 10. EU emblem.

The sentence used in PILOTING project to announce the EU co-funding is the following:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871542”

14. Conclusions

The deliverable 10.2 Exploitation and Dissemination plan, produced within WP10, has provided an overview of the exploitation and dissemination phases during the whole project lifetime, presented the main tools, as well a list of consortium activities.

On one hand, the main objective of the Exploitation Plan is to maximize the number of technologies that will be exploitable and industrialized after the end of the project. This deliverable has detailed the methodology agreed by PILOTING consortium to achieve this objective, as well as all its features that will ensure the effectiveness of PILOTING project was presented.

The main exploitation tools which will be used within PILOTING project will be: innovation sessions to take an overview of the most promising value propositions, interviews with end-user during pilot experiments, the Value Proposition Canvas model to evaluate the value propositions identified and generate and Business model for each one and the agreed IPR management of PILOTING outcomes. Furthermore, the initial key exploitable results have been presented, as well as the exploitation plans both at partner level and scenario level at this stage of the project. Also, a roadmap for the future industrialization of the results is presented. Finally, the KPIs that will be used to evaluate and monitor the exploitation activities during the project lifetime have been presented.

On the other hand, the main objective of the Dissemination Plan is to promote and disseminate the PILOTING results and benefits to the potential end-users, the scientific community, robotics and the general public as well as well as to ensure the effective communication of the research undertaken in the PILOTING project supporting the needs of the relevant stakeholders.

This deliverable has defined the main dissemination and communication activities and tools which include: project website, newsletters, press releases, stakeholders’ workshops, training and special sessions, social media activities, technical and non-technical publications, clustering activities will similarly themed project, etc.

Finally, the Dissemination Plan establishes the procedure to be followed in dissemination activities, as well as the KPIs that will be used to evaluate and monitor the dissemination activities during the project lifetime.

Annex I: Flyer layout

PILOTING PROPOSES

THE ADAPTATION, INTEGRATION, AND DEMONSTRATION OF ROBOTIC SOLUTIONS, IN AN INTEGRATED PLATFORM, WHICH WILL BE TESTED AND EVALUATED IN THREE LARGE-SCALE PILOTS: REFINERIES, BRIDGES/VIADUCTS AND TUNNELS WITH THE INVOLVEMENT OF ALL THE ACTORS THAT CONFORM THE FULL VALUE CHAIN.

CONSORTIUM

The PILOTING consortium is made of 14 high-profile European partners, from six European countries, carefully selected for their acknowledged excellence as well as both their complementarity and transnationality in order to provide the necessary knowledge, expertise, and state-of-the-art background required to ensure the success of the PILOTING project as well as the sustainability of the proposed research and expected results.

PILOTING consortium includes high reputation research and innovation partners together with worldwide leading technological companies, highly specialized SMEs, inspection and maintenance service providers and companies that operates or owns infrastructures on both considered sectors (Oil&Gas and Civil Infrastructures/Transport).

Therefore, PILOTING consortium integrates the full value chain of the inspection sector (from technological providers to inspection service providers and asset owners) ensuring the industrial application and future exploitation of PILOTING technological developments.

PILOTS FOR ROBOTIC INSPECTION AND MAINTENANCE GROUNDED ON ADVANCED INTELLIGENT PLATFORMS AND PROTOTYPE APPLICATIONS

PARTNERS

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THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 871542

If you are interested in PILOTING project, please send an email to piloting-project@catec.aero to become a member of PILOTING User Group

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ABOUT THE PROJECT

CURRENT EUROPEAN REFINERIES AND CIVIL INFRASTRUCTURES, LIKE TUNNELS AND BRIDGES, ARE AGEING, AND THEREFORE GRADUALLY BECOME DETERIORATED, ESPECIALLY TAKING INTO CONSIDERATION THE CURRENT AND FUTURE ECONOMIC SITUATION IN EUROPE WHERE LARGE INVESTMENTS IN RENEWING INFRASTRUCTURES ARE NOT FORESEEN.

Then, it is paramount important to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities in order to keep the necessary safety levels in these ageing infrastructures. To overcome this important challenge, PILOTING proposes the adaptation, integration, and demonstration of robotic solutions, in an integrated platform, which will be tested and evaluated in three large-scale pilots: refineries (Oil&Gas sector), bridges/viaducts (Civil/Transport Infrastructure sector) with the involvement of all the actors that conform the full value chain.

The PILOTING integrated platform will demonstrate the application of robotics at scale in the domain of Inspection and Maintenance (I&M), reduce end-user commercial risks on the deployment of robotics in the sector, demonstrate capabilities and improve understanding of robotics uptake value, develop and support the related ecosystem around the piloting I&M operations, as well as, contribute to industrial standards in robotics for I&M.

CHALLENGES

THE MAIN FOCUS OF PILOTING PROJECT IS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY AND QUALITY OF INSPECTION AND MAINTENANCE ACTIVITIES IN ORDER TO KEEP THE NECESSARY SAFETY LEVELS IN AGEING INFRASTRUCTURES. TO ACHIEVE THIS INCREMENT, THE INSPECTION & MAINTENANCE INDUSTRY IS FACING THE FOLLOWING MAJOR CHALLENGES

CHALLENGE 1

Current inspection methodologies are based on manual inspection procedures which are low-speed and require, most of the times, infrastructures' shut-down. The use of robotic technologies in PILOTING will importantly decrease cost and time of inspection and maintenance.

CHALLENGE 2

Nowadays inspection authorities and personnel lack in using repeatable and reproducible inspection data, often found deficient in quality measurements. Errors in or limited quality of inspection measurement data can have important consequences that may lead to damages to the infrastructure or health risks to the public or infrastructure personnel. PILOTING will provide high precision measurement data (gathered by the robotic vehicles) structured and presented in a seamless but trustworthy approach towards the inspection personnel and maintenance teams following international and well-established reporting approaches.

CHALLENGE 3

Personnel access and probability of accidental falls and injuries represent the predominant cost of the inspection. Having personnel working on elevated structures and dangerous locations requires planning, presence of support personnel, which implicitly implies slow progress in the measurement operations. PILOTING will contribute to increase personnel safety through advanced and automated robotic systems.

OBJECTIVES

IN ORDER TO OVERCOME THE IDENTIFIED CHALLENGES, PILOTING HAS ESTABLISHED THE FOLLOWING OBJECTIVES

OBJECTIVE 1

Adapt advanced robotics supported by artificial intelligence technologies to the end-users needs and increase their technological readiness levels for the three considered scenarios.

OBJECTIVE 2

Design and develop the PILOTING I&M open and scalable platform.

OBJECTIVE 3

Integrate the full value chain to demonstrate benefits of the PILOTING technological developments through large-scale pilots in real conditions and infrastructures.

OBJECTIVE 4

Overcome current barriers in inspection and maintenance robotics.

OBJECTIVE 5

Support to the promotion of European robotic solutions within the inspection and maintenance industry.

Annex II: Roll-up layout

PILOTS FOR ROBOTIC INSPECTION AND MAINTENANCE GROUNDED ON
ADVANCED INTELLIGENT PLATFORMS AND PROTOTYPE APPLICATIONS

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Annex III: Poster layout

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 871542

OBJECTIVES

OBJECTIVE 1
Adapt advanced robotics supported by artificial intelligence.

OBJECTIVE 2
Design and develop the PILOTING I&M open and scalable platform.

OBJECTIVE 3
Integrate the full value chain to demonstrate benefits of the PILOTING technological developments.

OBJECTIVE 4
Overcome current barriers in inspection and maintenance robotics.

OBJECTIVE 5
Support to the promotion of European robotic solutions within the inspection and maintenance industry.

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